

D.6.3 - Policy Brief

Policy briefing in contexts of territorial accumulation

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Executive Summary

This document compiles various policy briefs on different thematic areas. It is the result of the work of the Critical Policy Analysis (CPA) group of the Contested Territories Network based on the proposed scientific agenda. Within this group, over the years, we have discussed critical positions regarding decision-making by public officials, leaders of social organizations, and activists in non-governmental organizations. As part of the CPA group, we have engaged in discussions about territorial accumulation in policy processes driven by different actors. Common theoretical frameworks in Latin America and Europe have been discussed, reflecting the diversity of perspectives held by the individuals who make up the Network.

This report constitutes a second deliverable compiled by CPA. It revisits some discussions from our first document, corresponding to deliverable D3.2: Working Paper 2: Comparative Critical Policy Analysis on Territorial Accumulation. However, in this deliverable 6.3, we seek to condense the discussions we had during the formation of the group through various policy recommendations prepared by network members with individual track records in thematic work and a collective track record in collaborative studies.

The call was open to all participants in the Contested Territories network, regardless of individual group affiliation, and the result is reflected in this report. This document serves as a closing document for lengthy discussions on how to recommend actionable suggestions to experts in various fields.

Based on the written recommendations, the work of the project's scientists and activists relies on high-quality qualitative research that we believe will be highly useful for decision-making.

The topics addressed are derived from the themes proposed by the various members of the network. Therefore, the topics of housing, the use of cities, socio-environmental issues in different forms, and gender issues are presented here.

In addition to the recommendations by topic, this document includes a theoretical review of the policy briefs that served as the opening statement.

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Evidence-based policymaking and the policy brief:

a review of findings, challenges and alternatives

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Abstract

Research and policy-advising organisations are increasingly seeking to understand how data, evidence and knowledge shape the policy-making process: a trend which has increased as higher-education institutions place new emphasis on achieving societal impact. Much of this work focuses on the researcher-policymaker relationship, including practical prescriptions related to trust-building, understanding one's audience and effective communication. In the English-speaking world and increasingly globally the 'policy brief' has become the standard format to achieve this. However, critical research also shows that institutional frameworks, power imbalances, (geo)politics and culture directly shape the process of policy formulation, contributing to unforeseen effects and underscoring the observable differences in policy effectiveness and outcomes across regions and countries. This calls into question the policy value of research evidence and the positivist paradigm underlying how that evidence is formulated and associated policies are developed. Against this backdrop, various alternatives to policy briefs have been advanced, particularly in Global South contexts such as Latin America. Marginalised communities are responding to the aforementioned challenges in an effort to pluralise the forms of knowledge which policy-makers engage with. Centring on a range of policy fields related to territorial development in Latin America, this report first provides an overview of what is currently understood about evidence-based policymaking across the region and various uses of policy briefing within this. It secondly shows how politics and power are given growing consideration as outcome determinants, and highlights associated calls for researchers and policymakers to engage with and interrogate underlying ontological and epistemological assumptions. Finally, the report presents and assesses several alternatives to policy briefs as vehicles through which marginalised residents in Latin America and the wider Global South may influence policies that affect their lives.

1. Evidence-based policy-making and knowledge translation

While every civilization has attempted to understand the effects of government decisions on people, only for “the last couple of centuries” has social science research concerted to move beyond the goal of understanding reality to also seek to influence policy (Langou & Weyrach, 2013: p.272). Indeed, research into evidence-based policymaking, broadly referred to as ‘policy science’, originated as recently as the 1950s.^[1] This varied literature, originating from academic and policy institutions alike,^[2] explores how scientific evidence affects policy formulation, implementation and evaluation (Evans and Cvictanovic, 2018; Felt et al., 2018; Servaes, 2020). One of the goals of this work is to understand how to make research more useful to decision-makers. The question has major national and international implications in policy areas such as public health, still one of the main realms for policy briefing, but is also increasingly relevant for the sustainable development agenda as funders require evidence on the quality and effectiveness of research in contributing to their theory of change (Belcher et al., 2017).

A major theme within studies of evidence-based policymaking concerns how the process of ‘translating’ research to different audiences necessarily alters its meaning (Tieu et al., 2023). It is recognised that researchers often lack direct knowledge or experience of policy contexts, requiring guidance on how to engage, communicate effectively and establish a productive relationship (Evans and Cvictanovic, 2018; Servaes, 2020). At the same time, author credibility significantly influences the uptake of research recommendations (Arnautu and Dagenais (2021), with research originating from African [and by extension, other Global South] universities typically viewed as lower- quality than those of North American and European universities (Fillol et al., 2022). It is further argued that knowledge translation is most effective when there is a sense of ‘shared endeavour’ which accounts for the mutually unfamiliar environments in which researchers and policymakers operate (Connelly et al., 2021), and the ‘common and opposite needs, interests and expectations’ of all involved (Langou and Weyrauch 2013, p.299).

Prioritisation of knowledge translation - that is, ‘getting evidence into policy’ - has led to important oversimplifications (Oliver et al., 2014). Models of the policy-making process have assumed a series of discrete ‘stages’, overlooking how policy problems and solutions are themselves inseparable and interconnected (Hallsworth et al., 2011). Similarly, research has overlooked the interdependence of research and policy in vivo, leading to undue assumptions about the uptake of research evidence, and calls for more critically and theoretically grounded research into policy-making within a dynamic, evolving interrelationship across research and policy arenas (Oliver et al., 2014).

The policy brief - or ‘policy note’ (Evans, 2014) - is among the most commonly used formats for the communication of research findings. Despite their widespread adoption, their effects have been shown to be nonlinear, with readers potentially following multiple routes ‘from belief to action’ (Beynon et al., 2012: p.68). It is further argued that policy briefs are more likely to influence the formation of new opinions rather than transforming existing beliefs (Masset et al., 2013). For this reason, researchers are generally advised to adapt the brief to the intended audience, and to introduce the brief as early as possible within the policymaking process (Felt et al., 2018). Further guidance includes clear definition of the problem, presentation of multiple alternative policy options alongside projected outcomes, and inclusion of a clear summary with key messages and recommendations (Felt et al., 2018). Elsewhere it is suggested that policy briefs which ‘give personality and form’ to the researcher through presenting personal opinion have the potential to foster a deeper relationship and greater uptake (Beynon et al., 2012: p.68). Nevertheless, there remains a lack of social-scientific knowledge regarding how different policy brief formats, or alternative formats such as infographics, may suit different end goals (Arnautu and Dagenais, 2021).

2. Culture, politics and institutions

Research into evidence-based policymaking requires engagement with how cultural, political and institutional factors affect policy issues and decision-makers’ perceptions of them (Strydom et al., 2010). Yet, context has been historically disregarded in policy science generally and in studies into the uptake and effectiveness of policy briefs specifically (Arnautu and Dagenais, 2021),

[1] The term ‘policy science’ was first coined in the 1950s. See: <https://www.encyclopedia.com/social-sciences/applied-and-social-sciences-magazines/policy-sciences>

[2] In the UK, a 1999 government paper recognised that policymaking in prior years had become overly risk-averse and short-term (Hallsworth et al., 2011: p.22).

neglecting variations to the policy-making processes across different constitutional arrangements or where the relationship between civil society, policymakers and academic institutions differs substantially (Stein et al., 2006). Overlooking institutions as an expression of a precise political and cultural setting can be especially detrimental when the policy in question is aimed at transforming those very institutions (Stein et al., 2006).

Early research into evidence-based policymaking relied on overly simplistic models of the state and the actors which exert an influence on government decision-making. Long and Ploeg (1989: p.240) emphasises a tendency to 'reify state institutions' and to thereby neglect 'inter-agency struggles' in the design and implementation of policies. The authors further highlight how the state negotiates its decision-making power with a variety of socio-economic interests, allowing them in many instances to affect or control policy decisions (Ibid-p.241). Moreover, only recently has attention been paid to how both 'outsiders and insiders' shape how policy issues are framed, with policy responses shown to potentially mobilise protest movements rather than demobilising them as was conventionally thought (Pettinicchio, 2012 p.507). Rather than a simplistic binary, the state-movement intersection has also been shown to involve individuals who are members of the movement while holding positions within the state itself (Banaszak, 2005). This complexity demands consideration of how policy programmes are transformed through their implementation (Long and Ploeg, 1989: p.242).

A number of studies have explored the relationship between political institutions and policymaking in Latin America.^[1] As democracy surged in the 1980s, the 1989 Washington Consensus led to increased concern with the timing and implementation of government policies, though a 'one-size-fits-all' approach failed to consider how policy decisions are actually navigated (Seaigh, 2000). In the 2000s, development organisations like the Inter-American Development Bank explored how different constitutions, legislative and electoral systems and interest groups influence public policies in the region (Saiegh, 2020).

Here it was found that countries with strong executive branches relative to the legislatures are more prone to policy instability, as are those with histories of one-party governments and electoral systems prioritising individual candidates rather than parties (Periera et al., 2011). In a review of policymaking in Latin America, Cohon (2009) suggests that in order to understand how policies diffuse across national borders in the region, less attention should be paid to multilateral institutions and more to their proponents within the state. The author further points to the unexplored role of sub-national actors and officials, particularly in the wake of decentralisation policies.

A decisive factor for policymaking in Latin America and the wider Global South pertains to how major socio-political phenomena affect policy-makers' incentives. Stein (2006) suggests that institutional transformation is most easily achieved when political shifts or crises create a 'window of opportunity' that clarifies the costs of no change, before a group of actors adopts new ideas, viewing them as consistent with their own interests. Gilardi and Wasserfallen (2019) similarly note the significance of the electoral consequences of policy decisions, suggesting that the stage at which issues are defined is crucial to understanding how policymaking responds to external factors. In a study on Chile, Murillo and Foulon (2006) find that crises can lead to policies receiving more rapid support, yet if such crises coincide with electoral competition, policymakers may be more likely to rush through new policies with less regard for the possibility of uncertain effects. Similarly, Fairfield and Garay (2017) find that electoral competition is likely to stimulate redistributive social and tax policies, and that while such reforms may be more limited under conservative governments, social mobilisation can counter business interests and direct incumbents' attention to "securing social peace and surviving in office."

3. Ontological politics and the legitimacy of scientific knowledge

Research institutions appear to have moved away from a linear model of the research-policy relationship (Maas et al., 2022), with the process of evidence-based policymaking now seen as a "complex, dynamic and integrated sociological phenomenon" (Tieu et al., 2023: p.1).

[3] In one of the first English-language articles on policymaking in Latin America, Hirschman (1975) offers several binaries through which to categorise policy problems. These include 'pressing' vs 'autonomously chosen' problems; 'privileged' vs 'neglected' problems; and problems for which motivation outweighs understanding and vice versa

At the same time, NGOs are increasingly called upon to support alternative models of development through building alliances with civil society actors (Beggington et al, 2007). Both academic institutions and NGOs appear to embrace their role in driving positive transformation in the Global South and elsewhere, as evidenced by their apparent receptiveness to pluralistic notions of knowledge which prioritise the lived experience of marginalised groups (Tieu et al., 2023). Despite these promising discursive shifts, in practice, policy-making continues to depend on reductive models which limit the potential of alternative forms of knowledge to be incorporated into policy-making processes.

Notwithstanding the emergence of critical and interpretivist perspectives and methodologies, the positivist paradigm remains largely dominant within research institutions. The associated attention on 'evidence' is problematic for democratising and pluralising policy decisions, because it is ill-equipped to account for how values shape policy decisions (Greenhalgh and Russell, 2009: p.304). One clear way that this manifests is the continued prioritisation of 'academic' literature by research organisations and policymakers alike, at the expense of 'grey literature' which may be more pertinent to social movements and the communities they represent (Davidson, 2017).

A second challenge relates to the reductive treatment of politics as something to be 'managed' rather than engaged with or deconstructed (Hallsworth et al., 2011: p.12). Answers to fundamental ontological questions such as 'what there is in the world, how things fit together, what causes might have what effects' are treated as 'value-free, hard evidence, statements of fact' (Yuielle, 2023: p.2). Conversely, practical decisions about 'what to make visible to politics' are treated as apolitical, rather than fundamental to the 'ongoing struggle to define what the world is like' (Ibid: p.2). These hidden assumptions allow for the persistence of linear models and the continued foregrounding of certain voices at the expense of others, thereby prohibiting the development of an "attractive alternative imaginary of science-policy practices" (Maas et al., 2022).

Thirdly, emergent concerns regarding the perceived validity of scientific knowledge have led to efforts to defend traditional forms of scientific inquiry. The 'post-truth' era refers to the idea that there exists a web of actors which collectively undermine the legitimacy of scientific evidence, while disseminating disinformation at the expense of democratic decision-making and public well-being, significantly altering how policies spread within and across countries (Gilardi and Wasserfallen, 2019). This has resulted in new concerns regarding the need for a counterbalance which ensures that scientific evidence - as conventionally understood - maintains a degree of 'epistemic primacy' (Tieu et al., 2023).

4. Transformative alternatives to the policy brief

Policy briefs are rarely used in isolation, but as one tool that research organisations adopt within a "multi-pronged influencing approach" (Beynon et al., 2012: p.74). As research institutions appear to embrace different sources of knowledge, a multitude of other processes and activities have emerged which bring together academics, policymakers, practitioners and the broader public in the process of policy formulation, implementation and evaluation (Hinrichs-Krapels et al., 2020). This section introduces some of these alternatives and their application with marginalised groups in Latin America and elsewhere, and offers some brief insights regarding their effectiveness to democratise the process of policy-making.

4.1 The Policy Lab

A Policy Lab is a process of engaging with citizens on the development of public policy. Their use has surged in recent years, with over 100 in existence across the globe (Whicher, 2021) - including several in the Latin American region.^[4] Unlike policy briefs, Policy Labs are not intended as a 'standalone event', but instead designed to establish trust between a diverse group of participants and to synthesise research into a generally understandable format (Hinrichs-Krapels et al., 2020 p.3). Evidence indicates that Policy Labs can create a 'safe space' for the expression of opposing views, especially if they intentionally involve participants with alternative perspectives, and through that can illuminate barriers to policy implementation and create opportunities for the co-production of solutions (Olejniczak 2020 p.106).

[4] In 2014, the UK government established a multidisciplinary Policy Lab team as part of wider efforts to "make policy making more open" which works across local and national government departments and with external organisations. See: <https://openpolicy.blog.gov.uk/about/>. A Policy Lab has also been established which focuses specifically on Latin America. See: <https://www.region360.org/policy/>

Furthermore, Policy Labs are flexible and can follow a different methodological process depending on the policy area or stage of policy development (Hinrichs-Krapels et al., 2020: p.3).

While the potential of Policy Labs across different settings remains under-researched, there appears to be significant optimism about their use in Latin America. Writing on the city of Cali and the surrounding Cauca Valley, Colombia, Escobar (2018, p.195-197) posits that Labs, conceptualised as “organised conversations for action” can underpin more radical and speculative ‘design imaginaries’ through grappling with fundamental (ontological) questions such as ‘What do you want Cali to be?’ However, the lack of typologies and comparative studies means that more research is needed to understand what makes Policy Labs both organisationally sustainable and effective in the long-term (Olejniczak, K. et al. (2020: p.105). As such, it is broadly recommended that Policy Labs be used as one tool within a broader process of policy development (Hinrichs-Krapels et al., 2020).

4.2 Legislative theatre and transformative storywork

The effective communication of scientific evidence must create a ‘policy narrative’, through the telling of “good stories” that are both engaging and appeal to policymakers’ emotions (Davidson 2017). Among the creative approaches adhering to this logic, the Legislative Theatre approach invites the audience to participate directly in a theatrical performance and, through this, to decide the outcomes of the story told. Considered the founder of this method, Augusto Boal (1998) first implemented Legislative Theatre in his home city of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, as a means to motivate local people to produce legislation and ‘create a truer form of democracy’. Building on the critical theories of Paulo Friere, this process has also been referred to as ‘Theatre of the Oppressed’.

Since its inception, Legislative Theatre has been implemented in partnership with a wide range of socially and politically marginalised groups across the Global South (Kuftinec, 2018; Elliot, 2021). Writing on its application with a group of women in Afghanistan, Saeed (2015: p.300) notes the potential of Legislative Theatre to create opportunities for participants “to speak out and

have their opinions heard.” Reporting on its use with a group of refugees in Israel, Kuftinec (2018 p.171-172) argues the method can create “a different kind of citizenship and belonging” that “legislates the refugee into civil society.” However, political change through this approach is dependent on partner organisations setting aside their own goals and necessities and working for the benefit of participants (Elliot, 2021).

Another innovative methodology which potentially links research to policy-making is storytelling or ‘transformative storywork’ (Wheeler et al., 2020). Participants are invited to construct an individual or collective story, and empowered to tell that story through a range of creative methods and formats. On its application in South Africa, Wheeler et al., (2020) emphasises how this approach can reveal structural injustices, deconstruct power relations and stimulate relational learning. Elsewhere, on digital storytelling workshops with immigrant women in Toronto, Canada, Brushwood Rose and Grande (2013) show how the evolution of stories over time creates ‘unexpected self-expressions’ which have a significant yet under-researched value. As testament to the growing uptake of this approach, an ongoing research project involving a multidisciplinary team of researchers is applying a comparative storytelling methodology across Colombia and South Africa, with the goal of producing new knowledge on crisis representation, facilitating cross-regional knowledge exchange and ensuring that crisis response policies align with the needs of marginalised urban residents.

4.3 Neighbourhood planning

Neighbourhood planning represents another arena wherein research on/with marginalised groups can be used to affect policy-making. Proponents of engaging residents in local planning decisions argue that this can “pluralise the range of voices and sources of knowledge” considered in government decisions that affect residents (Yuille, 2023 p.1). In the UK, a growing body of interdisciplinary research is uncovering a ‘hidden history’ of local people challenging official planning decisions and advancing alternative land-use plans.

Research also explores the factors which undermine engagement in formal planning decisions, particularly in deprived areas, including the significant organisational and technical capacities required, as well as the need to balance competing interests (Parker and Salter, 2016).

[5] The project is entitled ‘Interrogating Urban Crisis Representation and Response in ‘Disorderly’ Southern Cities’. See: <https://www.thebritishacademy.ac.uk/projects/interrogating-urban-crisis-representation-and-response-in-disorderly-southern-cities/>

In Colombia, successive city administrations have promised to strengthen citizen participation in local governance, as part of efforts to incorporate peripheral neighbourhoods into their domain. However, such policies have disguised a secondary motive of undermining the influence of non-state actors (Stienen, 2020), while classifying citizens according to their vulnerability and demanding they adhere to certain behaviours (Zeiderman, 2013).

If research has revealed a range of barriers to resident engagement in local governance, there remains significant yet unexplored scope for academic institutions to actively support marginalised groups to affect planning policy. This can be achieved through facilitating the co-production of knowledge and by supporting community-based organisations to develop the capacities necessary to engage in the process. A participatory (action) research project in Colombia seeking to understand the complex local dynamics of the 'post-conflict' era successfully brought together residents and the Buenaventura municipal government in the co-creation of a city plan for peace.^[6] In this instance, as in other participatory research projects, the production of knowledge and its potential impact is non-linear and intertwines throughout the research process.

5. Conclusion

This report provided a synthesis of current debates on evidence-based policy making. Amidst growing attention to achieving societal impact through research, the report argued that beyond establishing trust and 'translating' research to policy audiences, the social, political, institutional and cultural environment in which the policy process is embedded has a significant yet underexplored effect on policy outcomes - particularly for policy issues involving 'wicked problems' characterised by uncertainty and unpredictability (Olejniczak 2020, p.105). Presenting and synthesising research into policymaking in Latin America, the report calls for close consideration of the array of actors that directly and indirectly affect the policymaking process, the different effects of policy interventions at local and regional levels, as well

as the 'autonomous' forms of change that occur beyond the state (Long and Ploeg 1989: p.242).

The report further addressed the possibilities for pluralistic forms of knowledge to be incorporated into policy development. The varied literature cited in this report collectively suggests that both researchers and policymakers must move beyond a unidirectional science-policy model, and to instead embrace an 'alternative imaginary' that engages with the 'politics of knowledge' in such a way that includes a wider set of citizen voices (Maas et al., 2022). The report then presented a range of alternatives to policy briefs and their application in Latin America. It showed that research organisations that implement Policy Labs, Legislative Theatre, Transformative Storywork, and engage with Neighbourhood Planning, can contribute to deconstructing, democratising and decolonising policy-making processes. While it remains to be determined whether such alternatives are a 'temporary fashion' or will 'substantially change' how policies are developed in the long-term (Olejniczak et al. (2020 p.105), the report further showcases the potential for participatory research to integrate knowledge production with policy influence in a multi-directional process that foregrounds marginalised voices.

[6] See <https://www.peoplesplans.org/>

[7] See <https://www.ukri.org/who-we-are/how-we-are-doing/research-outcomes-and-impact/esrc/esrc-celebrating-impact-prize/previous-winners-and-finalists-2021/>

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Towards Fairer Rental Housing

Policy Recommendations from Southern Europe for the EU Housing Agenda

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Abstract

Key findings from a comparative survey on tenant conditions in Lisbon, Madrid, and Barcelona prove that private renting generates urban inequality and offers unstable and insecure residential conditions. In all three cities, private renting has become a widespread form of tenure marked by displacement pressure, financial strain, and deteriorating housing conditions. Far from being a transitional phase, private renting is now a structural condition affecting broad segments of the population, who are excluded from secure forms of housing tenure.

These findings call for coordinated EU-level action to protect tenants' rights and reduce housing inequalities. We propose a comprehensive set of policy recommendations aimed at strengthening tenancy security, regulating rents, discouraging speculation, expanding the public rental stock, and improving transparency in the rental market.

1. Key Survey Findings: The Reality of Renting in Southern European Cities

- *Renting is a structural intergenerational tenure:*

Rental housing has expanded significantly in the past two decades in all three cities and nation-wide (see Chart 1). Furthermore, renting is not just a temporary phase of young adults. Most tenants in all three cities are aged between 30 and 64. While youth is overrepresented in Barcelona, the majority of tenants are working-age adults who do not transition to homeownership.

Chart 1. Tenant population by city and country

- *Homeownership is no longer a universal expectation:*

Most tenants do not expect to buy or inherit a home. In Lisbon, less than 5% expect to purchase property. In Barcelona and Madrid, over two-thirds foresee no access to homeownership or inheritance (see Chart 2).

Chart 2. Tenants' answer to the question: will you inherit any home?

- *Unprotected contracts provoke residential insecurity:*

Most private rental contracts are with a fixed term and offer no real protection; when contracts expire, tenants are exposed to no-fault evictions, or rent increases in the cases of Madrid and Lisbon. Over the last decades, both Spain and Portugal have rolled back tenant protections, and indefinite or long term leases with low and controlled rents are slowly disappearing. In Madrid and Barcelona, over 80% of tenants have unprotected contracts, with a duration between 5 and 7 years. In Lisbon, 62% are in leases of three years or less. Furthermore, fixed term leases facilitate the conversion of residential units into temporary or tourist accommodation.

- *Rising rent burden generates financial stress:*

Between 30% and 40% of tenants spend over 50% of their income on rent. However, the vast majority of tenants are overburdened, spending more than 30% of their income on rent: 68,7% of the tenant population in Madrid and 71,4% in Barcelona face rent overburden. In Lisbon, the portion of the market with unprotected contracts faces the highest overburden rate (80%). Rent increases outpace income growth, pushing tenants into debt and financial precarity.

- *Forced mobility intensifies displacement pressure:*

One-third of tenants expect to move within the next year, often due to price increases or contract termination. Recent moves are frequently involuntary: 31.6% in Barcelona, 30.8% in Madrid, and 37% in Lisbon. Furthermore, tenant turnover is high in all cities studied. Around 6 in 10 tenants have lived in their current home for less than five years. Even in Lisbon—the most stable case—nearly half of tenants (49%) have changed residence within that time frame. In Madrid and Barcelona, the figures are 62.4% and 62.1%, respectively. In Buenos Aires, 63% of tenants have moved one or more times in the past five years.

- *Housing conditions reproduce material deprivation:*

Over 80% of tenants report serious housing issues, including poor insulation, humidity, or lack of heating in the three cities. Overcrowding and forced cohabitation are becoming more common, especially among lower-income and migrant households.

- *Rent extraction fuels asset-based inequality:*

Property ownership is becoming concentrated in the hands of a few. Beyond precarious residential conditions, tenants' rental payments are a transfer of wealth from the poorest segments of society to the richest one. Thus, residential property distribution and rent flows are increasingly relevant to explain socioeconomic inequality and urban segregation.

2. Policy Recommendations: a multi-pronged approach to rental security

In response to the increasing residential precarity experienced by tenants globally, public policy must not only mitigate the effects of housing insecurity but address its structural causes. Below is a set of policy measures designed to protect tenants and reduce asset-based urban inequalities. These proposals should be understood as interdependent and mutually reinforcing: isolated interventions may prove ineffective if not part of a broader regulatory framework (e.g. rent control alone, without regulation of short-term or tourist rentals, may fall short).

1. Introduce open-ended or automatically renewable contracts

The most effective measure to guarantee residential stability and protect tenancy contracts is to reintroduce contracts without a predefined end date, allowing tenants to remain in the dwelling as long as obligations are met. Contracts should only be terminated by the landlord for justified reasons, such as their own need for use, which must be demonstrated with no viable alternative housing options available.

Several EU countries (Germany, Austria, Denmark, Scotland, France, The Netherlands, Sweden) already provide such models. In Germany, most leases are indefinite and may only be limited in duration if a justified reason is given (e.g. personal use or planned renovations). In France and the Netherlands, contracts tend to be open-ended or long-term with automatic renewal, and termination is allowed only for specific reasons. In Denmark, automatic renewal is the norm unless valid grounds for termination exist. In the UK, legislative reforms are underway to end "no-fault evictions," aiming to eliminate arbitrary contract termination.

2. Implement rent controls

Introduce mechanisms that regulate rent prices to reduce financial stress and overburden on tenant households^[8]. Price controls not only alleviate the economic pressure but also curb displacement by preventing excessive rent hikes. Furthermore, rent regulation helps reduce inequality by narrowing the gap between landlords' returns and tenants' income capacity^[9].

3. Deconcentrate ownership and redistribute wealth

As the tenant population grows, increasing rental income is being transferred to landlords who concentrate property ownership. Rental income thus functions like a regressive tax and drives the wealth gap. Public policy must aim to reverse this trend through:

• *Restriction of speculative housing investment*

Homebuyers seeking a primary residence increasingly compete with wealthy investors using real estate as a financial asset. Several countries have introduced policies to curb this dynamic:

- **New Zealand (2018):** Banned non-resident foreign nationals from buying existing homes under the Overseas Investment Amendment Act.
- **The Netherlands (2022):** Enacted the Opkoopbescherming law, requiring buyers to live in a newly acquired home for at least 4 years before renting it.
- **Vancouver, Canada:** Imposed a 20% tax on foreign real estate buyers to cool the market.
- **Singapore:** Applies a steep Additional Buyer's Stamp Duty (ABSD), reaching up to 65% for foreign corporate investors and over 30% for second or third-time local buyers.

• *Progressive taxation of property and rental income*

Redistributive tax policies are key to addressing housing inequality. Property taxes should be scaled progressively based on the size of property portfolios and rental earnings. A OECD report indicate that advanced economies underutilize property taxation in favour of labour and consumption taxes, reinforcing inequality^[10].

4. Expand the stock of public and non-speculative housing

Lack of affordable rental housing –the reduced proportion of public, social or cooperative housing– is directly tied to the overproportion of for-profit housing stock. The expansion of public and non-speculative housing should prioritize permanence and ecological sustainability:

[10] Causa, O., Woloszko, N., & Leite, D. (2019). Housing, wealth accumulation and wealth distribution: Evidence and stylized facts (OECD Economics Department Working Papers No. 1588). OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/86954c10-en>

- **Permanent protection from speculation.** Revenues from property taxation should be used to acquire or retrofit housing stock into non-speculative, permanently affordable units.
- **Renovation over new construction.** Large-scale construction projects increase carbon emissions. Expansion should prioritize reuse and adaptive housing strategies.
- **Support public–community partnerships.** Promote models of collective tenure through land leases, such as the cooperative housing policies in Barcelona, which offer long-term use rights (50–100 years) on publicly owned land.

5. Facilitate public and collective purchase of properties

Expanding the protected rental sector cannot be solely based on large-scale construction. Mechanisms must be established to support public bodies and tenant collectives in acquiring properties on the private market:

- **Public right of first refusal** Cities like Berlin and Munich have advocated for reforms to restore strong municipal pre-emption rights. Barcelona is also another good example. Such rights enable public authorities to buy properties before they are sold to private investors to preempt future displacement of residents.
- **Tenant right to purchase** The Tenant Opportunity to Purchase Act (TOPA) in Washington, D.C., empowers tenants to buy their building when it goes on sale. Many form cooperatives with nonprofit support, preserving long-term affordability.

6. Prevent anti-social uses of housing

Protection of rental housing also involves preventing diversion to less protected or non-residential uses:

- **Tax vacant dwellings** Cities like Paris already levy taxes on homes left empty for long periods. These measures incentivize reintroduction into the rental market^[11].
- **Reduce and prohibit tourist rentals in high-pressure urban areas** In cities with strained housing markets, municipalities must be empowered to drastically limit or prohibit short-term and seasonal rentals. A recent precedent is Catalonia's Decree of urgent measures on the urbanistic regime of tourist apartments^[12], approved in November 2023, which applies to 262 municipalities. The law allows these localities to require time-limited urban planning licenses for tourist-use dwellings and to restrict their number in designated high-pressure areas. Under this framework, the municipality of Barcelona has announced it will revoke all tourist apartment licenses by 2028.

Together, these policies can reduce residential insecurity, improve housing conditions, and make urban life more equitable for tenant populations across Europe.

[11] Segú, M. (2020). The impact of taxing vacancy on housing markets: Evidence from France. *Journal of Public Economics* vol. 185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2019.104079>

[12] Generalitat de Catalunya (2023). *Decret Llei 3/2023 de 7 de novembre, de mesures urgents sobre el règim urbanístic dels habitatges d'ús turístic*. <https://portaljuridic.gencat.cat/ca/document-del-pjur/?documentId=971523>

3. Integration into EU Housing Policy

The issues highlighted in Lisbon, Madrid, and Barcelona are not isolated. They reflect structural transformations in rental housing across the EU. To protect the right to housing and reduce growing inequality, the European Commission should:

- Recognize rental insecurity and housing inequality as key priorities to address in the EU Urban Agenda.
- The criteria for defining what counts as “affordable” housing must be clearly established. Following the recommendation of the EU Urban Agenda Housing Partnership, the housing cost burden threshold should be reduced from 40% to 25% of disposable income. Moreover, definitions of affordability should account for variations in income levels. For households with lower incomes, even the 25% threshold may be too high and should be adjusted accordingly.
- The EU should establish a more enabling legal framework for public support to public, cooperative and non-profit housing providers, beyond narrowly targeted social housing for the most disadvantaged. This includes revising State aid rules to allow broader Services of General Economic Interest exemptions, facilitating investment in inclusive and affordable housing solutions across Member States.^[13]
- Mobilize EU funds to expand social and cooperative rental housing. Investment should be directed towards expanding public or public-cooperative ownership and renovation of the housing stock and not simply to build new housing and expand the urban fabric, in order to create a permanent housing infrastructure that is weathered from market-driven speculation.
- Funds for member states should be conditioned to the adoption of tenancy security measures, such as, re-establishing open-ended contracts, implementing new-generation rent controls, or deploying and anti-speculation tax frameworks to prevent residential accumulation.
- Establish that state subsidies for home purchases should require the property to remain free from speculation or rent extraction, prohibiting resale (or letting) above the CPI-adjusted purchase price. This would help integrate market-rate housing into rent- or price-controlled stock.
- Promote policy convergence and best practice exchange through the European Union members, in particular setting guidelines and regulations that guarantee tenants’ tenure security and the respect of tenants’ rights.

Conclusion

Rental housing is now a permanent reality for millions of Europeans. Without decisive public action, the expansion of renting will deepen inequalities and social fragmentation. This policy brief calls for a comprehensive approach to protect tenants, regulate markets, and ensure fair access to decent housing across Europe. The European Union must play a leading role in advancing a rental housing agenda that prioritizes dignity, stability, and social justice.

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Recommendations for the Public Policy on Gender Equality for Women in Valle del Cauca, 2024-2036

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Abstract

This public policy constitutes a significant collaborative effort to address sociocultural gaps affecting women living in the Cauca Valley. It is a legal instrument that promotes a situated understanding of human rights and comprehensive well-being from an inclusive and intersectional perspective. The following outlines the process, based on a descriptive description of its scope and an analysis of opportunities for improvement.

Part 1

Description of Public Policy

A Public Policy for Women is essential to:

- A. Reduce the historical, structural, and social gaps that have affected women.
- B. Promote and guarantee women's rights for their well-being and comprehensive development.
- C. Responding in a situated and intersectional way to the needs of women in the Cauca Valley.

Who is the Public Policy for Women aimed at?

To women from the 42 territorial entities of Valle del Cauca, with an emphasis on those in vulnerable situations.

The category of women is presented from the intersectionality and diversity of women's realities in the Cauca Valley and not as a unitary and homogeneous category.

It embraces the configuration of historical oppression, colonization, and the Colombian armed conflict against women.

Also included as interest groups are women's organizations, community-based organizations, feminist movements, human rights organizations, and other institutions working for gender equality and the protection of women's rights.

What are the objectives of the Public Policy for Women?

Improve equal access to the territorial development dimensions for women in the Cauca Valley. To achieve this, the specific objectives are:

1. Improve economic empowerment.
2. Better unequal conditions in access to the social dimension.
3. Improve access to institutional care in the department.

What is the scope of the Public Policy for Women?

The Public Policy for Women is framed in three lines based on its three specific objectives, six outcome goals, and 31 product goals:

Line 1. Economic Development of Women in the Cauca Valley. It seeks to improve women's empowerment and reduce monetary poverty through access to economic resources, property, assets, financial services, employability, training, employment, and the use of information and communication technologies. For example, the policy proposes reducing the gender unemployment gap in Valle del Cauca to 4.8% by the end of the public policy period.

Line 2: Development of the Social Dimension of Women in the Cauca Valley . These are aimed at the comprehensive well-being of women through the exercise of citizenship and equitable access to food security, healthcare, quality education, affordable energy, and safe communities. The program also recognizes the reduction of violence and discrimination against women, unpaid care and domestic work, and the guarantee of sexual and reproductive rights. For example, the policy aims to reduce the female suicide rate per 100,000 inhabitants in the Cauca Valley to 0.81 by the end of the public policy term.

Line 3: Development of the Institutional Dimension with a Gender Approach. Reaffirming the end of violence and discrimination against women, strengthening, coordinating, and ensuring guarantees at all levels of institutions, justice, and citizen security. For example, through the strengthening, recognition, and use of access and care pathways in the case of gender-based violence. For example, the policy aims to reduce the number of femicides in Valle del Cauca to eight by the end of the public policy's term.

What are the approaches and principles of Public Policy for Women?

Beginning

- **Human Dignity.** Seeks the recognition, respect, and guarantee of the rights of all people as equals.
- **Equity.** It aims to reduce the injustices and inequalities faced by women.
- **Diversity.** Recognizes the diversity of women in terms of race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, and life stage, and that programs, actions, and strategies must address them.
- **Social justice.** It involves transforming social and economic structures that maintain inequalities and injustices.
- **Sisterhood.** It involves strengthening ties between women to guarantee their rights.
- **Intersectional.** Recognizes the multiple forms of discrimination and oppression that women experience based on their age, gender, ethnicity, disability, and poverty, and the need for comprehensive and intersectional approaches.
- **Territorial.** This involves recognizing the territorial and regional contexts women inhabit and navigate, enabling them to design specific actions and lead decision-making. For example, rural, Afro-descendant, Indigenous, and peasant women.
- **Inclusive Ecology.** It addresses the interconnectedness and fair and equitable relationships between humans, animals, and nature to close social and environmental gaps.

Approaches

- **Human rights and citizenship building.** To guarantee equality and the enjoyment of rights given women's historical inequalities through the use of gender-sensitive mechanisms and citizenship building.
- **Gender.** Recognizes gender as a socially constructed category that has generated unequal distribution of roles, expectations, and opportunities, especially for women.
- **Differential population.** Recognizing diversity, we seek to ensure that public policies respond to specific needs in support of equity and equality.
- **Environmental.** Following the call of the Inírida Declaration of the 16th United Nations Conference on Biodiversity in 2024, the contribution and role of women in caring for life and preserving and managing the biodiversity of the territories and communities they inhabit is recognized.
- **STEM Education, Innovation, and Technology Focus.** Promotes women's participation, leadership, and professional development in underserved fields of knowledge, such as science, technology, mathematics, engineering, and the arts.

What is the jurisprudential line that precedes this Public Policy?

Among the international precedents are:

A. Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action .

It proposes, based on gender equality, a sustainable, peaceful, and inclusive world that defends and empowers girls and women.

B. 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development .

It is considered the roadmap for Latin American and Caribbean countries, prioritizing issues requiring special attention based on the problems on the international agenda.

C. Law No. 11,340 (Maria da Penha , Brazil).

Establishes the commitment to prevent and punish domestic and family violence.

D. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW),

ratified by Law 51 of 1981. It commits Colombia to eliminating gender discrimination in all its forms, adopting public policies and affirmative measures for effective protection.

At the Departmental level:

A. Decree 879 of 2020. Creates the Departmental Council for Women's Security to address security and gender violence on the public agenda.

B. Departmental Decree No. 1.22-1599 of September 16, 2024. Adjusts the administrative structure of the department and establishes the mission of the Secretariat for Women, Gender Equality, and Sexual Diversity, seeking to guarantee the human rights of women and the diverse population.

At the national level they are:

A. Law 294 of 1996 and Law 1257 of 2008

establish regulations to prevent and punish domestic violence and discrimination against women.

B. Law 360 of 1997 establishes rights for victims of sexual crimes, guaranteeing their access to health services, justice, and assistance.

C. Decree 4463 of 2011. Regulates Law 1257 of 2008, promoting the hiring of women victims of gender-based violence and establishing systems for reporting and preventing workplace harassment.

D. Judgment C-355 of 2006. This decriminalizes abortion in specific cases (rape, risk to the mother, fetal malformation) and has been reinforced by subsequent rulings to eliminate barriers to access, such as SU-096 of 2018 and C-055 of 2022.

E. Law 581 of 2000 and Law 2424 of 2024. Guarantees the participation of women in senior public positions, promoting parity.

F. Law 1761 of 2015 (Rosa Elvira Cely Law). By which femicide is classified.

What gaps does the updated Public Policy for Women aim to address?

- A.** The need to update and integrate emerging challenges became more visible and accentuated by the COVID-19 pandemic. For example, women's labor force participation in the second quarter of 2020 in Colombia was 43.9%, while men's was 66.2%. Valle del Cauca saw the largest increase in the incidence of monetary poverty among women between 2019 and 2020, by more than 10 percentage points (25.2% to 35.79%).
- B.** The historical, social, and structural inequalities and inequities that continue to significantly affect women. For example, in 2021, Colombia had a high prevalence of pregnancies between the ages of 16 and 19 compared to other countries in the region. In the same year, in Valle del Cauca, 75.8% of women earned one minimum monthly wage or less, compared to 59.8% of men.
- C.** The social, regulatory, territorial, and economic changes that the country and the Department of Valle del Cauca have experienced over the last decade. For example, the unemployment rate, peacebuilding and security, and the structure.

Part 2

A reflection on opportunities for improvement

How was the Public Policy for Women agreed upon?

With the participation of 2,637 people, women, institutional actors, sectors and groups.

During 2022, four citizen participation meetings were held in the Central Subregion (Guadalajara de Buga) with 137 women, the Pacific Subregion (Buenaventura) with 233 women, the Northern Subregion (Cartago) with 113 women, and the Southern Subregion (Cali) with 110 women.

Seven in-depth discussions were held: in Commune 10 of Cali, in Andalusia with a panel focused on women victims of the armed conflict in rural areas, a women's camp in Cali with two groups of women from various municipalities, a panel with community mothers, another in Buenaventura with territorial leaders, in Candelaria with local leaders from the municipality, and another in Cali with women with disabilities and the community women's network.

Two semi-structured interviews were conducted with experts in the field of women's rights in the region.

Discussion panels were held with representatives from the Ministries of Health, Sports, Education, Culture, Social Development, Territorial Peace, and others.

A total of 1,576 women from the Department's 42 municipalities participated, answering a public policy questionnaire on topics such as the labor market, household conditions, health, political participation, discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity, among others.

It was organized by the Secretariat for Women, Gender Equality and Sexual Diversity of the Valle del Cauca Governorate.

What conclusions can be drawn from the Public Policy for Women 2024-2036?

A. Policy responds to the harmonization of departmental, national, and international policies, financial management instruments, contemporary women's demands, and the social, regulatory, territorial, and economic changes experienced by the country and the Department of Valle del Cauca.

B. Inequalities in access to territorial, economic, social, and institutional development undermine the overall health of women in the Cauca Valley.

C. According to DANE (2020), 53% of the population in Valle del Cauca are women and 66.3% of them are located in socioeconomic strata 1 and 2 (DANE National Quality of Life Survey, 2021).

D. In Valle del Cauca, 25.0% of households are headed by women and 8.8% by men.

E. Women in the Cauca Valley are prominent in caregiving and life-sustaining work, with an unequal distribution of caregiving responsibilities and urgent need to recognize them in order to close gender gaps.

F. Extreme monetary poverty among women in Valle del Cauca has increased between 2018 and 2021, likely related to the COVID-19 pandemic.

G. Gender-based violence, monetary poverty, mental health, and the transformation of gender perceptions, representations, and stereotypes are cross-cutting issues that must be articulated to strengthen the territorial development of women in the Cauca Valley.

What are the limitations of the Public Policy for Women 2024-2036?

A. A descriptive diagnosis is presented with key indicators related to the Economic, Social, and Institutional Development of Women in the Cauca Valley. This is insufficient given that it lacks an analysis from a differential, gender, and intersectional perspective. For example, the ethno-racial, sociocultural, ability, and sexual and emotional identity characteristics, as well as how these relate differentially, are not specified. Including this information contributes to highlighting the needs and specificities of the communities and would provide a more focused orientation for the Policy's action plan to respond more broadly to the required transformations.

B. Priority is given to the argumentation of the Policy based on and with statistical and numerical data related to deficits and gaps, minimizing positive and proactive approaches to the processes, achievements, and progress of women throughout history in the Cauca Valley, based on their female voices and narratives.

C. A life course approach that integrates the gaps affecting women throughout their diverse needs, capabilities, opportunities, and trajectories, in the interaction of biological, psychosocial, economic, and environmental factors, is not evident.

What recommendations can be made to Public Policy?

A. Public policy must explicitly challenge discussions regarding the hegemonic construction of women, feminized bodies, and feminine subjectivities.

B. Public Policy presents Timid approaches to the categories: woman, women, and feminine. These are named without achieving depth or recognition of ethnic-racial, territorial, sexual, generational, and affective-relational diversity. This generates public policy with a prominent cisheteronormative and whitewashed bias.

C. Recognize women's diversity in terms of their ethnic origins, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation, age and life trajectories, territorial mobility, religions, physical characteristics, and abilities.

D. A public policy is needed that makes visible the processes led by women in the transformation of social, structural, and historical gaps.

E. Integrate diversity-sensitive indicators and figures into diagnostics and require official statistical systems and observatories to include specific cases and narratives of women and collectives in the Cauca Valley, embracing their own ancestral and popular knowledge in a georeferenced and intergenerational manner, reflecting the processes and progress made in gender throughout history.

F. It must be ensured that monitoring, tracking, and evaluating public policy is carried out in a transdisciplinary manner and with public participation, allowing for appropriate adjustments.

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Cali Afro public policy

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A. What is the Cali Afro public policy?

The Cali Afro public policy is a government initiative of Santiago de Cali (Colombia), aimed at improving the living conditions of the Black, Afro-Colombian, Raizal and Palenquera communities (hereinafter NARP).

NARP communities live in low-income neighborhoods on the urban periphery. According to the DANE census (2023), Cali has 2,280,522 inhabitants, of whom 21.6% identify as Afro-descendant.

According to Agreement 0459 of 2019, public policy seeks to:

- 1 Respond to the social problems that affect the population.
- 2 Guarantee access to rights and opportunities within the framework of the Social State of Law enshrined in the Political Constitution of 1991.
- 3 Promote cultural recognition and political representation of NARP issues in institutional bodies of local public administration.

The jurisprudence underlying this process is based on Agreement 0459 of 2019, Law 16 of 1972, Law 22 of 1981, Law 70 of 1993, and Convention 169 of the International Labor Organization. These considerations refer to the right to equality, the free development of personal and ethnic identity, sanctions against discrimination and aporophobia, and the promotion of citizen participation.

B. What is the objective?

The objective of public policy is to guarantee the fundamental rights of NARP communities (Agreement 0459 of 2019), emphasizing the recognition of ethnic diversity and territorial needs.

Such approaches focus on the inclusion and democratic openings required to subvert the social injustices faced by communities.

Its specific objectives are:

- Ensure the reduction of sociodemographic vulnerability.
- Improve access to and retention in the education system.
- Establish a monitoring system for labor dignity and racial equity.
- Guarantee health and pension coverage.
- Guarantee the financial, technical and human resources for its development.
- Strengthen the CaliAfro Program technically, operationally, and financially.

C. What is its origin?

The Cali Afro public policy originates in the struggles for political recognition of the NARP communities. These processes have taken place from the late 20th century to the present day and involve various lessons learned from the National Constituent Assembly that cemented the 1991 Political Constitution (Quevedo-Pérez, Noriero-Escalante, Hinestroza-Valencia, 2020). The following timeline is presented on this subject:

D. What problems do the populations participating in this public policy face?

NARP communities face deep inequalities, exclusion, and structural racism. According to DANE (2018), these communities represent 9.34% of the Colombian population (4,671,160 people), with a high territorial dispersion (97.68% of municipalities). In the department of Valle del Cauca, 30.6% of the inhabitants are NARP.

Structural inequalities affect access to fundamental rights such as health, education, and employment. The unemployment rate among Afro-descendant women is 21.5%, 10.8 percentage points higher than that of men. Furthermore, 66.8% of this population works in the informal sector.

Regarding education, only 14% have access to higher education, and 6.1% have no training (DANE, 2023).

In 2020, 38.38% of the NARP population was a victim of the conflict, and 98% of Palenqueros and 37.5% of Afro-Colombians suffered forced displacement (National Information Network, 2020).

Between 2018 and 2022, 957 social leaders and human rights defenders were murdered, many of them in NARP territories (INDEPAZ, 2022).

The pandemic exacerbated the impact by increasing poverty and inequality. Despite government efforts to implement a solidarity income, the crisis had a negative impact on women, early childhood, and youth (DANE, 2018).

These externalities, caused by social isolation, generated the economic crisis that led to the 2021 National Strike, with the Aguablanca district being one of the epicenters of the social unrest in Colombia.

Other data to consider according to DANE (2018):

24.5%
of the NARP population lives in multidimensional poverty

8.5% +
more than the national average.

26.3%
of NARP households have internet access, creating a digital divide.

71.3%
Consider themselves poor, compared to **46.7%** of the country as a whole.

E. What does public policy propose?

These initiatives seek to reduce inequality gaps, promote cultural recognition, and guarantee equal access to opportunities in education, healthcare, and employment.

It proposes the implementation of citizen participation mechanisms to address discrimination and aporophobia and consolidate social inclusion.

This approach is based on three actions:

1. Training processes on human rights issues for the NARP population.
2. Tables and consultative spaces for social and community participation.
3. Citizen oversight and monitoring of resources invested within the framework of public policy.

F. What are the current problems that can be addressed with this public policy?

- 1 The lack of coordination between government entities and civil society organizations interested in the realization of Human Rights in the territories inhabited by the NARP population.
- 2 Economic inclusion within the framework of employability and entrepreneurship. Public policy encourages business sectors to participate in alliances that contribute to overcoming the externalities caused by multidimensional poverty.

- 3 Addressing structural racism through campaigns that promote cultural recognition of the NARP population and their contributions to civic life. It is also committed to the collaborative development of strategies to raise awareness of ancestry.
- 4 Economic inclusion within the framework of employability and entrepreneurship. Public policy encourages business sectors to participate in alliances that contribute to overcoming the externalities caused by multidimensional poverty.

G. What do civil society organizations require to integrate into the scope of public policy?

To achieve this, NARP territories must have an institutional offering capable of integrating expectations of cultural recognition, economic redistribution, political representation, and environmental justice, among other reasonable demands that foster dialogue between communities and state entities.

Municipal and district budget resources must be allocated to implement programs in education, health, economic inclusion, and access to housing. To this end, community needs must be characterized and consultation groups established to incorporate consensus into the action plan resulting from public policy.

Community citizen participation ensures the constant updating of territorial assessments and also allows for the framing of social justice perspectives. This requires promoting leadership and agency capacities through training in the legal and constitutional procedures that enable the realization of rights in the territories.

Finally, transparency mechanisms are needed to help compare public actions among participating entities.

H. What achievements stand out?

Since its implementation in 2019, achievements have been limited because the pandemic and current social circumstances have made it difficult to access the public funds required for the implementation of actions and interventions. Despite this, the following are noteworthy:

1. The development of educational and technical training programs to promote job inclusion. In this regard, participation in entrepreneurship and employability experiences is highlighted.
2. The inclusion of the differential approach in the Municipal Development Plan has been achieved, which would facilitate the implementation of actions derived from public policy.
3. The customs and habits of NARP communities have been highlighted in cultural and sporting events, which contribute to the consolidation of Valle del Cauca's identity.

i. What are its limitations?

Despite the legal and constitutional conceptualization, there are gaps between what policy expects and what NARP communities experience.

Institutional policies still fail to guarantee the rights of this community due to the contingencies of the last five years and the institutional racism represented by bureaucracies that impede access to public resources.

The lack of democratic participation represents a limitation. While there are methodologies for consensus-building, their impact is limited because it requires civic education that allows for the generation of common goods and solidarity pacts.

More cross-sector partnerships are needed to foster convergence between civil society organizations and government agencies. These types of experiences foster the leadership and agency capacity of NARP communities.

Finally, access to the public budget is required to enable the implementation of actions arising from public policy.

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We invite you to listen to the Public Policy Comparison podcast on YouTube.

Chapter 1: <https://youtube.com/watch?v=x11uPKjQIMU&feature=shared>

Chapter 2: <https://youtube.com/watch?v=x11uPKjQIMU&feature=shared>

"Complete Streets" in Informal Contexts:

Recommendations for Managing Pedestrian Space in the Popular Neighborhoods of the Reconquista Basin (RMBA)

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Executive summary

The study proposes adapting the "complete street" concept to contexts of high social and environmental vulnerability, such as the working-class neighborhoods of the Reconquista Basin (Buenos Aires Metropolitan Region).

To this end, it recommends classifying streets and alleys based on their dimensions, materials, basic services, environmental risks, lighting, and commercial and public transportation presence. This classification will lay the groundwork for targeted policies tailored to local conditions and demands.

The importance of applying participatory methodologies—such as collective mapping, audited walks, and digital tools—that allow for gathering information based on residents' everyday experiences is emphasized. In this process, "territorial coordinators," community leaders with knowledge of the neighborhood, play a key role.

There is also a need to train local labor and municipal technicians to execute projects using adapted criteria, as well as to implement more flexible service delivery systems, such as condominium networks. Phased planning, consistent with available resources, is recommended, allowing for progressive adjustments.

Finally, key variables for monitoring interventions are identified: level of use, maintenance, safety, waste management, housing and commercial improvements, and community participation.

Introduction

The Complete Street concept, coined and disseminated in North America since the early 2000s, proposes reducing the hegemony of the automobile, Improve pedestrian safety and increase active mobility by offering universal design recommendations and parameters. However, its application in contexts of the Global South, and particularly in informal settlements, requires adaptations sensitive to specific socio-environmental realities.

With this approach, the nodes of the School of Habitat and Sustainability (National University of San Martín) and the School of Geography and Planning (University of Sheffield) collaborated in the development of these recommendations for the treatment of pedestrian space in informal contexts. The study focused on two popular neighborhoods — 8 de Mayo and Costa del Lago — located in the Reconquista River Basin in the Metropolitan Region of Buenos Aires (RMBA), characterized by high social and environmental vulnerability.

In these settlements, open common areas—primarily streets and alleyways—channel daily mobility, while also serving as spaces for socializing and expanding overcrowded housing and small businesses, in direct contact with the sidewalk. Thus, the poor state of the infrastructure, flooding, poor lighting, and accumulated waste, among other recurring problems, affect both people's safe and continuous movement and their quality of life.

Fig. 1. Children playing in the street, 8 de Mayo neighborhood. Source: Bella Flor cooperative photographic archive.

In this context, the application of participatory methodologies—such as collaborative mapping and audited walks—allowed the identification of the main obstacles to pedestrian circulation, as well as areas perceived as unsafe or inaccessible by residents. Furthermore, the use of a QGIS plug-in facilitated the collection of geolocated images and the real-time recording of conflicts and deficiencies in pedestrian infrastructure. These inputs allowed for the construction of a diagnosis that articulates technical information with the daily experiences of those who live and travel in the area.

The project worked hand in hand with the Directorate of Socio-Urban Integration (DISU) and the Undersecretariat of Territorial Approach of the Municipality of San Martín. Over the past few years, these local government departments have built a network of neighborhood representatives, known as "territorial articulators," which allows for more effective and widespread outreach to the local community.

At the same time, we have partnered with the Proyectar Igualdad cooperative and the Rincón de Esperanza soup kitchen, which have played a key role in the urban development of Costa del Lago and 8 de Mayo, having led the installation of drinking water and sanitation networks, and the paving and lighting of streets.

Fig. 2. Daily journeys, drawing made during the collective mapping workshop at the 8 de Mayo community center. Source: CITTA, 2025.

Policy recommendations

A. passageway typification :

Towards comprehensive design solutions Based on the diversity of streets and passageways identified in the study neighborhoods, it is essential to construct a "catalog" of representative road sections, from which specific design guidelines can be established.

The distinction between settlements and villas provided by RENABAP for the 1,560 popular neighborhoods of the RMBA constitutes a first step in this classification. While the urban layout of the former attempts to reproduce the structure of the formal city, giving continuity to the size of the blocks and the existing street layout, the villas are organized around an intricate road system, with variable street widths and discontinuous sidewalks, whose connections often depend on narrow corridors that cross private properties.

Other aspects to take into account for this classification include: the existence of services basic services (running water, electricity and sewage system), the different widths of roads and sidewalks (if they exist), the materiality of the pavement (loose

soil, compacted soil or soil improved with cement, concrete), the presence of public transport and associated stops, the commercial and productive activity in front, as well as the type of lighting and green cover.

At the same time, the delimitation of critical areas (flood-prone, unsafe, with accumulated waste, etc.) through collective mapping exercises constitutes a fundamental layer of information.

It's clear that limiting vehicle traffic on the streets studied isn't enough. In fact, due to the low motorization rate, pedestrian and public transportation are the dominant modes of transportation . Added to this is the narrowness of certain streets, which only allow pedestrian traffic.

Fig. 3. Corridor, dirt road, and communal street built with the Socio-Urban Integration Fund (FISU), respectively. Source: CITTA, 2024.

Previous experiences, such as the consolidation of roadways and sidewalks, the implementation of interlocking pavements, and sustainable drainage systems, demonstrate an understanding of the shared and multiple uses of road space, as well as the high risk of flooding.

Such experiences have also highlighted the difficulty of leveling sidewalks, given the different levels of settlement of homes on uneven, potentially unstable landfills. The result of urbanization processes in these cases is continuous roadways and discontinuous sidewalks, which impacts the use of the former as pedestrian circulation spaces.

Fig. 4. Level discontinuities on sidewalks, 8 de Mayo neighborhood. Source: CITTA, 2024.

B. Implementation of co-evaluation methodologies for public space

Community participation from the earliest stages is a necessary condition for the co-evaluation of public space and the generation of situated solutions based on real needs.

In addition to individual and collective mapping exercises, audited walks, and other stakeholder engagements, several recent studies agree that mobile technology can foster a more participatory and dynamic approach to urban assessment than traditional methods. In our case, real-time data collection using a smart app (QGIS plug -in) phones, allowed to have updated information about the state of the streets.

Fig. 5. Survey of sidewalk widths and obstructions to pedestrian mobility. Source: Urban Planning Workshop (EHyS, UNSAM), DISU, 2024.

Fig. 6. Field survey using the QField mobile app . Photos: Guido Peric , 2025

Territorial articulators play a fundamental role in this task, acting as intermediaries between university professionals and local government representatives and neighborhood residents. These are community leaders, recognized for their work in soup kitchens, community centers, churches, or cooperatives, or simply for their longevity in the neighborhood, who can provide information in both directions.

The results of this set of participatory methodologies reveal, among other things, the most frequently used routes and the reasons for travel, as well as the reasons for choosing certain routes and perceptions about the use of road space. This strategy allows for prioritizing the treatment of certain streets or passages, favoring incremental or phased planning tailored to local demands, rather than pursuing the implementation of a complete road layout and improvement plan in a single phase.

While it is necessary to study the forms of verbal and graphic communication with residents (for example, avoiding technical terms in questionnaires and interviews, or including neighborhood reference markers on base maps), the use of participatory mechanisms should not "infantilize" or underestimate grassroots knowledge. It is also suggested to work with open guides, marginal notes, and other flexible tools for discovering and incorporating local knowledge.

Fig. 4. Level discontinuities on sidewalks, 8 de Mayo neighborhood. Source: CITTA, 2024.

C. From limitations to possibilities: in-person approaches, workforce training, and stagability of interventions

In informal settings, access to information is limited compared to other areas of the city. Tools such as Google Earth, Google Maps, or Street View, as well as other freely accessible satellite images or cartographic databases, have a limited reach in these areas, coupled with the scarcity or low representativeness of census data. Fieldwork also entails difficulties with physical access (blocked or flooded streets, poor public transportation connections), insecurity, the need for a neighborhood representative, poor cell phone service, and so on.

However, this type of in-person approach plays a fundamental role in gathering reliable qualitative and quantitative information constructed from the bottom up. It also stimulates creativity in generating one's own baselines from multiple formats—data, maps, testimonies—that inform about local specificities.

Another limitation is the shortage of skilled labor for the construction of special or atypical streets compared to those of the formal city. For example, residential streets with interlocking or permeable pavements, the construction of canals, filter drains, etc.

In this regard, it is recommended to train municipal technicians and residents who work in cooperatives to ensure that teams are prepared to replicate these types of solutions in other low-income neighborhoods.

land ownership issues and the progressive subdivision of plots be considered, testing alternative methods for accessing drinking water and sanitation services. For example, through "condominial" systems with shared connection points between groups of lots and dwellings.

Finally, frequent budget limitations require considering the phasing of the intervention, appropriate to available resources. This can become a useful tool for calibrating projects and introducing adjustments as the works are developed in conjunction with the local community.

D. Identification of critical monitoring and evaluation variables

In the context of the study, critical variables that would allow monitoring and evaluating the impact of the interventions include:

- levels of street and passage usage (by day and time slots)
- Within the above, levels of inclusion from a gender and age perspective;
- maintenance of pavements, street furniture and vegetation (situation and perception);
- changes in waste disposal methods and the presence of micro-landfills;
- Pedestrian and personal safety levels (situation and perception)
- improvements made to homes and businesses in front of the house;
- levels of community participation in the care and/or improvement of public spaces

Measuring these variables will be very useful for making adjustments in subsequent stages of the intervention.

The use of mobile applications can be useful for monitoring interventions in real time, gaining greater insight into street and alley usage, as well as the opinions and suggestions of their users.

Fig. 8 Microgarbage. Photo: Guido Peric, 2025.

Conclusion

The Complete Street model requires a shift in approach for its application in informal contexts: rather than standardized designs and universal parameters, it is about building localized solutions based on the physical, social, and economic reality of each neighborhood.

The case studies show that, despite the precariousness, there is a social and organizational infrastructure—cooperatives, territorial articulators, community networks—capable of sustaining incremental improvement processes. The recommendations proposed here aim to articulate this capacity with flexible, scalable, and participatory public policies that recognize the street not only as a means of movement, but also as a space for living and coexistence.

Socio-environmental module

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Executive summary

The following module, organised in four reports, addresses policy recommendations in terms of socio-environmental problems. They are aimed at people who play roles as agents of state policy, activists in social organisations, people who work in non-governmental organisations, and those who work in multilateral credit and cooperation agencies, among others.

The environment as a problem has been on the agenda of decision-makers for more than fifty years. The United Nations Conference on the Human Environment, held in Stockholm in 1972, was a milestone. The many subsequent reports and international commitments understand the interrelationship between environmental, economic and social development. Thus, the **socio-environmental** category is used to describe those practices where the social action of specific subjects, in specific territories, is associated with a dispute over the use, management and mode of production of the environment. These spaces are crossed, in turn, by institutions that operate at local, national and international levels. By state public policy processes and by actions promoted by companies. The socio-environmental category generally operates in spaces of conflict over the exploitation and appropriation of nature. For many of these conflicts, it is the local communities that find the solutions.

The recommendations promoted in this policy brief are based on empirical evidence and favour the qualitative method. The contributors to the different chapters have a history of research and activism on issues related to the use and appropriation of the environment. We seek to emphasise that these recommendations are part of a production process, brought together by the network of Contested Territories, where field experiences are vital for the elaboration of guidelines.

On the other hand, the transformations of capital in the twenty-first century, and its different models of accumulation, update the issues and problems associated with the environment. For this reason, we agree with Jason Moore when he states that capitalism has exhausted the historical relationship in which it was produced. In his work "The End of Cheap Nature", Moore places labour, food, energy and raw materials at the centre of value relations. These relations are co-produced in the human-nature link. And there the human - extra-human nature is reconfigured, generating new conflicts and challenges.

For this module, various contemporary experiences will be collected where the environmental crisis, climate change, nature constructed by human-non-human realities are at the centre of thinking about alternatives. The works included in this module include a first report on "Territories of rural peri-urban production", where recommendations and guidelines on local food production with an emphasis on agro-ecological approaches and small-scale producers' organisations and, in a complementary way, the peri-urban as a space of habitat are addressed. The second report "Commercialisation, food chains and certification in Argentina" focuses on the experiences of short chains, associative initiatives for the sale of food products and certification of production. The third report, entitled "Nature as a product: conservation and touristification", looks at the ways in which nature is appropriated through a variety of mechanisms which, in many cases, displace local populations. Finally, the fourth report is on "Urban political ecology", which reflects on the environmental problem with a focus on large cities.

Report 1

Rural peri-urban production territories

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Under the description "rural peri-urban production territories", we will refer to the food supply areas located on the outskirts of large urban centres and used for agricultural production. These places are often in tension due to the progress of urbanisation on the one hand, and the extension of the agricultural frontier on the other.

Tension due to the advance of urbanisation appears in two registers, informal settlements and private gated communities. Competition for productive land is one of the main problems identified.

By the shift of the agricultural frontier we mean the displacement of extensive commodity crops which, by saturating rural land, in some cases, is advancing into the peri-urban areas, raising the alarm about the land traditionally used to grow crops for daily household consumption.

In addition to these tensions over space, there are other problems associated with socio-environmental issues that are becoming increasingly common. In intensive food crop production, synthetic chemical inputs are used to control weeds and common pests. The use of these types of products has raised concerns both on the side of those who produce and are in daily contact with these inputs, and on the side of consumers who demand food without agrochemicals.

The first to be affected by the model of synthetic chemical use, which we will call the conventional model here, are the people who work in production, who are exposed on a daily basis to products that can be harmful to their health, and on many occasions (Gárgano, 2022) have reported illnesses that have even caused death. When health is threatened by a problem related to the use of certain products, other ways of carrying out

agricultural tasks without using them have been devised, although this is not usually the most common, we find experiences of transition to agroecology, organic agriculture and other ecological agriculture.

Consumers have also warned against the conventional model, arguing in favour of the consumption of healthy foods, foods that recover their original flavour, among others.

As we noted at the beginning, we have also identified problems in these territories that are related to the way people who work in industry or farming establishments live. The settlement of the population in peri-urban areas reveals multiple problems related to access to services and infrastructure in general.

Based on three cases described below, we will make a series of recommendations based on the qualitative work that has been carried out in various research projects.

Fresh food production in Buenos Aires. Multi-agent agroecology experiences

In Argentina, agroecology as an issue is linked to the emergence of organisations of producers from the subaltern rural sector, to the actions of state institutions linked to rural development, and to research and extension groups from national universities. The case described here is associated with this plot.

The town of Florencio Varela is located in the southern part of the metropolitan area of Buenos Aires, in an area historically destined to food supply, first with migrant labour from European countries (mainly Italy and Portugal) and Asia (Japan). Nowadays, the production lands are worked by

labourers from the northern provinces of Argentina and Bolivia. A substantial change in the ways of working is that the people who work the land do not own their plots, but rent the place where they live and produce. This condition of precariousness is repeated in other areas of the AMBA and also in other conglomerates of large cities in Argentina.

The organisation "1610" is located in Florencio Varela and is made up of more than 15 families dedicated to horticultural production in transition to agroecology. This production strategy was installed in the organisation more than ten years ago following the recommendation of a rural extension agent from a governmental institution who advised those who produce. Moving away from the conventional model to agroecology was a gamble that began little by little in an experimental plot, and then some of the methods tested there were extended to the plots.

The change in production strategy meant not only eliminating synthetic chemical inputs in vegetable production, but also exploring other and new marketing channels, in which the National Universities have played a key role.

When they talk about their transition to agroecology, the emphasis of those who produce is on taking care of their own health as well as that of their consumers and the environment. And, they clarify that it is not only about replacing synthetic chemicals with biological preparations, but also about planning production differently, combining crops, among other issues.

As many of the research projects that promote the agroecological model announce, the transition takes time, because it establishes a different link with production. One of the challenges for people who produce from La 1610 is that this time is conditioned by access to land, which most of them rent.

The change from a production strategy to an ecologically based one was possible thanks to a set of institutional actors from the state and the capacity of the people who produce.

Agroecology and short circuits in central Chile: links between public programmes and the social organisation of rural women

In recent years, agroecology has emerged in Chile as a proposal promoted by both peasant organisations and public programmes to promote

production. From the perspective of social organisations, this discussion takes up historical demands for cooperativism and peasant associativity, strongly repressed during the military dictatorship (1973-1989), a period in which an agro-industrial export model was promoted and the autonomous organisation of the peasantry was persecuted.

In this scenario, groups such as the National Association of Rural and Indigenous Women (ANAMURI) have played a key role in repositioning the demands of the peasant world, proposing agroecology not only as a productive technique, but also as a political alternative. From this perspective, food production is linked to the right to a dignified life and to the protagonist participation of rural women as transformative subjects.

This approach was strengthened during the constituent process opened after the social outbreak of October 2019¹⁷. ANAMURI and other organisations proposed including in the new constitution the recognition, promotion and support of peasant and indigenous agriculture as the basis of food systems, promoting ecological and sustainable principles (Palma, 2022). Although the constituent process did not prosper institutionally, the debate managed to permeate both the social and state spheres, encouraging the Ministry of Agriculture (MINAGRI) to incorporate agroecological criteria more decisively into its policies and programmes.

A concrete example of this articulation can be seen in the "Peasant Market" programme of the Institute for Agricultural Development (INDAP), in conjunction with MINAGRI. This programme promotes agroecological practices and facilitates short marketing circuits, bringing producers - especially rural women - closer to urban consumers. To understand this experience on the ground, the case of the rural commune of Machigüe, in the Libertador Bernardo O'Higgins Region, is analysed. This area, marked by the coexistence of a powerful export-oriented fruit agro-industry and small-scale peasant agriculture, shows the tensions caused by the intensive use of resources, especially water, and by the pollution associated with the use of agrochemicals.

[17] From October 2019 to March 2020, a series of popular protests took place in Chile throughout the country, but with an epicentre in Santiago. The population mobilised, despite state repression, with diverse strategies, from popular meetings to massive street rallies against the neoliberal policies of recent decades.

Own elaboration: Left, image of agro-industrial production of table grapes. Right, image of a farmer's market stall. Both images are from the Commune of Marchigüe, 2022.

The women producers of Machigüe cultivate and process their products using ancestral techniques such as the use of natural fertilisers and biological pest control. At the same time, they face adverse structural conditions, such as poor access to resources, limited transport and low connectivity. In this context, technical support from professionals and the opening of weekly marketing spaces help to mitigate some of these barriers. The farmers' fair not only functions as an economic space, but also as a meeting place with consumers, where relationships are built based on trust, knowledge of the origin of the food and recognition of the farmers' work. Short circuits thus acquire an ethical, territorial and relational dimension.

From a gender perspective, these spaces generate transformative effects. In territories where traditional roles are more deeply rooted, participation in agroecological production and direct sales gives women economic autonomy, public visibility and renewed self-esteem. Productive work becomes a source of social recognition, challenging stigmas that have historically relegated women to the domestic or reproductive sphere.

In this context, initiatives such as the National Agroecology School "Sowers of Hope", promoted by ANAMURI, deepen a feminist, popular and territorial vision of agroecology. Through training spaces, women collectively reflect on health, food, the body and care, situating agroecology beyond agricultural management, as an integral political project for the transformation of daily life and territory.

In short, the expansion of agroecology in central Chile shows a strategic convergence between institutionalism and social organisation. On the one hand, public programmes such as INDAP provide technical, logistical and commercial support to agroecological experiences. On the other hand, peasant women's organisations give political and community meaning to these practices, claiming their role as guardians of territory and food. This articulation between the institutional and the popular is fundamental for building fairer, more sustainable and gender-sensitive models of production and consumption.

Agroecology and short circuits in central Chile: links between public programmes and the social organisation of rural women

The case of the formation and consolidation of the Cordón del Plata neighbourhood shows the historical relationship between the political, social and economic-productive spheres.

The neighbourhood began when the "El Álamo" Cooperative acquired, in 1987, ten hectares, previously dedicated to the production of vines and fruit trees, in order to locate housing. The reconstruction of the history of the neighbourhood shows that, towards the end of the 1980s, the families of agricultural workers sought to consolidate their presence in the territory and to provide the next generations with access to services that were only possible in a peri-urban location. These services were mainly related to access to the public education and health systems.

Work in intensive agriculture in Argentina has been characterised by different contractual forms that have been modified and adapted to the productive and technological changes that have taken place in this area. One of these contractual forms included the provision of housing for the worker and his family, whose members also provided labour for different tasks and stages of the production cycle on the farms. These contractual forms were modified as the need for temporary labour diminished and workers and their families sought to change their residence in order to build a broader horizon for the new generations. From the late 1980s until now, the pressure of housing on the territories has only increased, accompanying the productive changes that increased the demand for local and migrant temporary labour, the migratory processes from neighbouring countries, especially Bolivia, which added to the impoverishment of living conditions in Argentina's large cities. These factors possibly led to the "return" of families who had sought employment opportunities in the urban area to their place of origin. This can be seen in the notable population increase in the department of Tupungato, which between 2010 and 2022 grew by 23%, exceeding by ten percentage points the total population growth of the province for the same period (Municipality of Tupungato).

Productive uses of the territory.

To understand the process of population growth in the Cordón del Plata neighbourhood and its relationship with broader socio-productive processes, it is necessary to consider its geographical location.

The neighbourhood is located on Route 96, known as "El Álamo" street, 18 kilometres south-east of the city of Tupungato, capital of the municipality of the same name. At a distance of 6 kilometres to the west of the entrance to the neighbourhood we find the provincial route 89 and on it there are many wineries, restaurants and lodgings that make up the "Gualtallary circuit", one of the tourist-productive circuits with the greatest international investment in the area. Also, one kilometre from the entrance to the neighbourhood, we find the Alco factory, a fruit processing and packing plant for which the neighbourhood provides a large volume of labour. However, the area is also home to a number of rented or owned farms, mostly run by Bolivian families of producers who have specialised in the

production of different types of vegetables for the domestic market and also in the production of garlic for export.

In short, this is an area historically oriented towards agricultural and agro-industrial production, which in the last thirty years has undergone technological-productive transformations involving national and foreign investment, mainly in the production of wine for export, but also in the integration of tourist circuits for the consumption of high quality food and beverages. These processes have transformed the territory in a notable way, revealing contrasts and tensions not only between the different productive uses of the territory, but also between these and the uses for housing and the services that this entails. In other words, within a few kilometres, we find gastronomic and tourist businesses oriented only towards the high purchasing power public and areas where the inhabitants coexist in different stages of settlement in neighbourhoods that entail different situations with regard to the possibility of accessing basic services characteristic of the urban plant.

The continuous population growth puts pressure on the services provided by the state in various sectors such as education, health, public transport, infrastructure works and the informal housing market.

Based on the cases we have selected, we make a series of recommendations for decision-makers, both from state institutions and other organisations that have a territorial impact:

- Preserve the peri-urban areas of cities as supply centres for localities by promoting agro-ecological or other ecologically based agriculture. This generates soil preservation, population rootedness in the rural-urban interface and quality food supply and proximity for the cities.
- Facilitate, through institutional programmes, technical assistance for people who produce and want to transition to ecologically based strategies.
- Access to land and water for those who produce in an agro-ecological way, by conditioning payment rates according to the time of work and harvest.

- Points of sale and distribution of agroecological or ecologically based products so that the circulation of goods is carried out through short channels where the distinction of not using synthetic chemicals is valued.
- Promote women's leadership in the production and sale of agroecological products and encourage a feminist, popular and territorial debate on agroecology.
- Simplify the requirements for access to electricity, drinking water and waste collection services in peri-urban territories destined for housing.
- Reorganise the availability of public transport to improve access to higher education for young people in peri-urban areas.
- Improve primary education infrastructure in peri-urban areas.
- Consolidate channels of dialogue between municipalities and representatives of peri-urban dwellers.

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Report 2

Commercialisation, food chains and certification in Argentina.

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Concentration in food marketing

Food marketing systems are highly concentrated. They are characterised by the presence of companies with dominant positions that condition the determination of prices on the shelves and in the production and marketing chain as a whole. For example, for the year 2022, it was found that 20 companies control 74% of the turnover of products on the shelves (CEPA, 2022).

In the case of fresh foods, such as fruit and vegetables, the traditional marketing circuit is channelled through wholesale concentrator markets, whose logic is linked to the seasonality of the products and the available supply. In Argentina, 80% of fresh vegetables are marketed in wholesale markets (Instituto Nacional de Tecnología Agropecuaria, INTA, 2023). This circuit is characterised by atomised production (a large number of producers who do not reach the volumes and quality demanded) and marketing concentrated in a small number of wholesale operators. This circumstance leads to information asymmetries that give wholesalers an advantageous position, allowing them to set prices according to seasonal and cyclical supply volumes, favouring speculative actions. This is compounded by transport and logistical difficulties that have an impact on costs for both producers and consumers: 80% of production travels more than 50 kilometres to reach a marketing point, and 40% more than 200 kilometres (INTA, 2023).

In this context, alternative marketing experiences are being developed in the field of the Social, Solidarity and Popular Economy (ESSyP), which seek to transform the forms of production, distribution and access to food in order to challenge the dominant marketing models. On this path, they aim, among other objectives, to promote agroecological

production, reduce intermediation and agree on convenient prices for both producers and consumers.

As a result, it has been found that solidarity intermediation marketers provide healthier and cheaper food to consumers, reducing the number of intermediaries (Centro de Estudios Scalabrini Ortiz, CESO, 2024). Likewise, it was identified that the evolution of the prices of the basic food basket goods in the alternative marketing spaces of the ESSyP tends to be slower than in supermarket chains. Specifically, it was found that between December 2023 and February 2024 the basket in the ESSyP marketers had a growth rate of 16.27% while in supermarkets it was 19.07% (CESO, 2024). It is striking to note that, in times of political instability, the evolution of prices in large supermarket chains can more than double, as happened after the August 2023 Open, Simultaneous and Mandatory Primaries in Argentina, when inflation in large supermarkets was 20 per cent compared to 9 per cent in alternative retailers (CESO, 2023).

In a complementary manner, the potential of ESSyP marketers is highlighted as the possibility of generating greater consumer awareness by maintaining direct relations with producers, promoting the consumption of healthy, fresh and safe food, and, at the same time, contributing to reducing environmental impact (INTA, 2023).

However, these spaces face numerous difficulties. At the macro or sectoral level, they have to deal with a high degree of market concentration, tariff policies, a volatile exchange rate, tax requirements, scarce financing for production, high input costs, and logistical and administrative barriers to marketing (Caracciolo and Foti, 2013). At

the micro level, there are also limitations such as the lack of legal and accounting management capacities, precariousness and overexploitation of labour, and insufficient income for those who participate in these experiences (Vázquez, 2016). In this context, access to financing becomes a strategic tool to stabilise and strengthen associative enterprises.

In this way, the food trade has become an arena of dispute that intertwines environmental issues, food issues and agro-industrial production systems. In order to understand these environmental and food struggles, we take as central evidence a federation of cooperatives called Alta Red. This report draws on knowledge from that experience and more general data and information provided by other research and secondary sources.

Alta Red is a federation of worker cooperatives engaged in solidarity food intermediation. It was formally constituted in 2022 after making joint purchases since 2018. It is made up of seven cooperatives: Más Cerca es Más Justo Me.Co.Po, Kolmena Oeste, Colectivo Solidario, Mercado Territorial, Productores a Consumidores and Caracoles y Hormigas. These organisations were previously dedicated to the commercialisation of fresh food, mainly seasonal vegetables and fruit, produced in the peri-urban area of the city of Buenos Aires. To this end, they worked with local horticultural producers organised to produce in an associative way and with the deployment of state policies and actions by public universities.

The aims of these activities were focused on transforming the forms of production, distribution and access to these foods in order to challenge the dominant models of production and commercialisation. These aims were based on agro-ecological production, reducing intermediation and agreeing on prices based on a price structure that was convenient for both producers and consumers.

The aim of changing the way food is produced is to eliminate the use of synthetic chemical inputs in order to reduce environmental damage and harm to the health of both producers and consumers. For this initiative to succeed, the actors involved understood that they had to organise the demand for such production by promoting its consumption and its differentiation from conventional production. Organising demand also implied organising the intermediation between producers and consumers.

1. Determining the fair price: costs, seasonality and symbolic factors

The experiences of alternative food marketing can be approached from multiple perspectives: as short marketing circuits, in the framework of public policies, from the social, solidarity and popular economy (ESSyP) approach, or from theoretical discussions around reciprocity, the processes of food valuation in solidarity intermediation, or the socio-spatial practices that explain their emergence and sustainability (Arzeno, 2022). These initiatives are characterised by shortening the distances between those who produce and those who consume, acting as bridges between rural and urban areas. It is not only about bringing products from the countryside to the city, but also about establishing links that communicate the struggles behind these products - such as decent, associative or self-managed work, and agrarian reform (Arzeno, 2022).

A key dimension in these experiences is the construction of the price, which aims to fairly remunerate those who produce and at the same time offer accessible prices to those who consume. This process is not limited to a market logic based solely on material or utilitarian costs, but incorporates immaterial and symbolic factors. Thus, consumption becomes a "political act" and food becomes an ideal of sovereignty (Dziencielsky and Laborda, 2020:34). For Coraggio (2008), these symbolic elements - such as the rational use of resources, local development and bonds of trust with consumers - must be incorporated by the ESSyP when describing their activities. However, the author points out that these experiences often lack the tools to make these aspects visible, which is why the state and organised society should provide strategies for dissemination.

This way of constructing value and price can also generate tensions: for example, as mentioned at the beginning of this report, at certain times of the year, certain products can have higher prices in solidarity intermediation marketers than in traditional supermarkets. This is because, while conventional chains lower prices in times of high supply - thereby reducing producer remuneration - solidarity marketers tend to maintain base prices that guarantee fair remuneration, which can result in less competitive prices. Added to this is the instability of demand throughout the year, which prevents the establishment of stable economic links with those who produce, making the interpersonal ties that are woven within the framework of these experiences all the more important.

The progress of these organisational processes for the transformation of food production and commercialisation systems has led to the search to expand the supply of products with the aim of providing the greatest possible quantity of goods from the basic food basket and thus cover the greatest possible number of products required by households. This led to the search for suppliers of fresh produce and non-perishable foodstuffs produced in other regions of the country. It required a leap in collective organisation since, in order to purchase products from more distant regions, it is necessary to reach a higher volume of demand that justifies the logistics and to have a space for collection and withdrawal.

Generally, producers ask for payment upon delivery. Given the characteristics of this form of commercialisation, this is not possible, as consumers pay when they pick up their orders and the traders pay for them at that moment and, if they pay in cash, on the next delivery. This means that Alta Red does not have the necessary funds to make the payment until approximately one week after receipt of the order. Therefore, payments are generally scheduled between one week and ten days after receipt of the order. This is an aspect that requires establishing trust with suppliers and also concerns the issue of financing.

A considerable number of experiences do not have the financial backing to stock up, nor do they have the space to store products for replenishment. In an economy with high levels of inflation and also in a context of devaluation, this puts solidarity-based intermediary marketers at a clear disadvantage compared to the hegemonic ones.

Based on these problems, we have developed four proposals:

- 3 Establish a programme of subsidies for the payment of rent for storage and distribution spaces.
- 4 Generate guarantee/equity guarantee programmes for the payment of these rents, since often the solidarity marketers are not creditworthy subjects who can apply for guarantees proposed by financial institutions at prices in line with the income generated.

2. The problem of food certification

At the international level, as a result of the emergence of particular production systems associated with the implementation of forms of food production that are differentiated according to their health and/or nutritional qualities and/or with the aim of avoiding or moderating environmental damage, food certification systems have been created. The most widespread are the certifications of organic products.

In Argentina, these systems are regulated by the Organic Production Law, No. 25.127/99. These certification modalities are known as "third party" modalities, which means that the control process is carried out by a private entity, generally companies, which is not part of the production system and is not linked to consumers or to the sectors in charge of marketing, thus guaranteeing the transparency of the process.

This form of regulation and control has expanded, mainly to access external markets, mainly the European Union. It is therefore a widespread modality among the export food producing sub-sectors and more likely to be adopted by business-type organisations. Lastly, organic certification systems do not assess any additional aspects other than those linked to the production system.

On the other hand, between universities, state institutions and social organisations, progress has been made in the design of "participatory guarantee systems" that allow for the endorsement that production has been carried out in an "agroecological" manner. This modality is aimed at supporting the transformation of production systems, improving the living conditions of producers and guaranteeing

- 1 Develop a programme of state purchases from solidarity marketers, aimed at acquiring products for school feeding programmes and community canteens, which would make it possible to build sustained demand over time.
- 2 Establish a micro-credit programme to support cooperative production and working capital, in order to reduce the mismatch.

access to healthy food for consumers. Its aims are broader and more ambitious. On the other hand, they are based on the participation of all actors involved (producers, professionals, agents of state institutions, academics, marketers and consumers). Despite its progress and extension over several years, the agroecological form of production does not have a state regulation that gives it an entity, and this form of regulation is not contemplated in national legislation.

The PROBLEM, then, lies in the need for a system of regulation and validation of specific food production modalities whose implementation is possible for small-scale fresh food producers, which would make it possible to identify and differentiate this production at the commercial level, provide confidence to consumers and prevent the designation from being used indiscriminately.

Proposals:

- 1 Generate a meeting and debate between different experiences at regional, national and sub-national levels to generate a proposal for legislation aimed at the promotion, creation of institutions and regulation of agroecology.
- 2 Promote exchange between cooperative marketing networks in the European Community and Latin America based on fair trade, the promotion of local economies and care for the environment.
- 3 To make visible, among the participants of the marketing and production experiences, state agents and private sector actors, the need for institutions and regulations that strengthen the processes of transformation of fresh food production and trade, focusing especially on sub-national levels of government.
- 4 Provide financial support for the design and experimentation of systems to guarantee the agro-ecological quality of production.

3. Recognition of alternative forms of organisation

In terms of their organisational forms, social and solidarity economy initiatives propose an alternative logic to the hegemonic capitalist model, based on principles of solidarity, cooperation and sustainability. These forms, driven by cooperatives, family farming networks, consumer associations and other entities in the sector, are distinguished not only by their organisational structure, but also by the values they promote at each stage of the economic circuit. The value they generate is not only economic: it is also social and environmental. Decisions are made with the participation of its members, prices are constructed to take into account the real costs of production and to guarantee a decent income.

Unlike traditional capitalist enterprises, these experiences do not seek to maximise profit, but are oriented towards satisfying the concrete needs of their members and communities. The surplus, when

there is one, is reinvested in strengthening the collective project and is not distributed according to the capital contributed, but according to work, commitment or needs. The prevailing logics are those of reciprocity, redistribution and cooperation, which give rise to economic relations based on trust, mutual care and respect for the commons. These practices seek to democratise the economy from below, generating processes of self-management and real participation that, in many cases, question hierarchies and traditional forms of authority. In this sense, the social, solidarity and popular economy represents not only an economic alternative, but also a political and cultural commitment to build other forms of life that are fairer, more equitable and sustainable.

In these organisational forms, value is not defined solely in terms of profitability or market price. There is a resignification of value that takes multiple dimensions into account: the way in which production is organised (collectively, democratically and based on bonds of trust), the traceability and transparency of the production process, as well as the overall quality of the product. In this way, social and environmental well-being is prioritised over profit maximisation, and a different economic logic comes into play, which recognises those who produce and consume as active subjects of a structural transformation.

Recognising the value of these organisational forms is key to their development and sustainability. In this sense, the following proposals not only directly benefit those who consume, but also strengthen the organisations that support this other economy, promoting fairer, more democratic and sustainable models of production, marketing and consumption:

- 1 Design and implement public food education campaigns: responsible food.
- 2 Design and implement public policies for consumer education: both in relation to responsible consumption and financial education.
- 3 Establish concrete incentive and recognition mechanisms for the sector, through tax deductions for marketers and/or refunds to consumers for purchases made in ESSp spaces.

Report 3

Nature as a Product: Conservation and Touristification

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Introduction

Since the consolidation of the environmental crisis as a matter of public interest towards the end of the 20th century, numerous environmental policy instruments have been created. One of the most influential concepts in addressing the problem is that of sustainable development, which questioned traditional economic development in order to incorporate the planet's biophysical limits into human development and balance social inequalities. Thus, it was defined in the 1987 Brundtland Report as "development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs."

The adoption of sustainable development contributed to the creation of common environmental action frameworks for most countries, facilitated flows of technical assistance and funding, and incorporated the discussion on the role of local communities in environmental conservation initiatives. However, more critical perspectives observe other effects of this approach, arguing that, by being incorporated into the capitalist framework, it has lost its transformative potential. This is due to the fact that certain environmental policies tend to produce new spaces of wealth concentration and deepen social inequalities. For example, carbon credit markets allow the transfer of atmospheric pollution permits in exchange for valuing carbon capture as an ecosystem service; or the reintroduction of extinct species into their "natural" habitats using nature-based tourism as an incentive. The proposal, then, is to rethink the environmental crisis by understanding the political foundations that underpin the current economic model, which results in environmental degradation and the reproduction of unequal social relations.

Below, we present five case studies that address the complexities of environmental management within the framework of sustainable development, understood as a space for valuing nature in terms of the benefits it provides to humanity.

Case 1: Environmentalisation Process in the Paraná River Delta, Argentina: Conflicts Regarding the Sustainability of Agricultural Activities

The Paraná River Delta (Argentina) is located at the distal end of the La Plata Basin, at the confluence of the Paraná and Uruguay rivers, covering an area of 1.75 million hectares under the jurisdiction of three provinces (Buenos Aires, Santa Fe and Entre Ríos) and nineteen municipalities. Since the 1990s, the Paraná Delta has been affected by an environmentalisation process: it has been revalued as a natural space capable of providing goods and ecosystem services to society. As a result, this historically marginal region has come to occupy a central place in the political practice of environmental non-governmental organisations (NGOs) promoting its conservation.

In the delta, zones of conservation, environmentally sustainable use, and—one might argue—sacrifice zones coexist. Over the last thirty years, multiple conservation designations have been established, recognised at supranational (international) and national levels, including areas protected under public ownership, mixed regimes (combining public and private land), and private ownership (i.e., private nature reserves).

In addition to protected natural areas, the region contains zones with different productive profiles: mass and elite tourism, cattle ranching, forestry, silvopastoral systems, and other smaller-scale activities. To ensure the environmental sustainability of agricultural practices, the production of multiple environmental best practice manuals has been the principal governance strategy.

These manuals, developed by state institutions and environmental NGOs, aim to encourage residents to self-regulate. In addition, these actors have established certification schemes to verify compliance, in order to guarantee the sustainability of production practices.

Particularly in the Forest Core Zone (Buenos Aires province)—the region specialised in poplar and willow cultivation located in the central part of the delta—the arena of conflict has focused on disputes over water management techniques. Initially, this involved the formation of two opposing coalitions: those defending traditional production methods (arguing that the construction of dykes and water-retaining embankments is essential for island life) and those advocating for wetland conservation (arguing that any water management technique posed a threat). Subsequently, the construction of mechanisms for collaboration between (certain) better-capitalised local residents, state agency officials and technicians, and environmental NGOs made it possible to defuse the conflict, through the production of best practice manuals, the development of sustainable production units, and the use of new water management techniques (such as double-entry pumps that allow both the inflow and outflow of water). However, evidence shows that this conflict resolution “rests” on the visibility of some and the invisibility of others, thereby perpetuating (not necessarily intentionally) the marginalised position of certain groups based on social class, gender, nationality, or ethnicity.

Case 2. Role of Local Communities in the Management of Protected Areas in the Paraná River Delta, Argentina

One of the most widespread ways of protecting ecosystems from human encroachment has been through the creation of protected areas (PAs). While this model initially proposed the exclusion of human presence, the prevailing paradigm today includes the adoption of participatory approaches. Within this model is the Ciervo de los Pantanos National Park (PNCP), located in the southernmost continental portion of the Paraná Delta wetlands (Buenos Aires, Argentina).

In the management of the PNCP, an approach that includes the community is sought; however, in practice,

this is not easy to achieve. To date, there are only specific projects that involve nearby residents, who participate in particular activities such as controlling exotic species or planting native species, but there are no comprehensive plans that rigorously aim to work with the entire community. This may be due to multiple factors: among them, high staff turnover, the absence of a specialised team dedicated to community engagement, a lack of budget, and inadequate techniques for working within the social sphere.

Case 3. Nature Tourism in the Canary Islands, Spain

In the case of the Canary Islands, Spain, tourism is the predominant economic activity. It currently represents 37% of the archipelago's GDP and employs 26% of the working population, but it is also responsible for 80% of the region's CO₂ emissions. This activity became established in the coastal zone, where the most significant transformation and artificialisation of land has taken place since tourism began in the 1960s.

Historical evidence shows changes in the use of the area through three stages:

- 1 **Coexistence** of tourism with other activities such as agriculture and fishing, concentrated in a few locations but carried out intensively.
- 2 **Government strategy** from the mid-1990s aimed at increasing the quality of tourism services, facilitating the introduction of new infrastructure focused on luxury tourism and transport.
- 3 **Recent expansion**, in which the modification of the Land Law (2017) facilitated the declaration of public interest for tourism projects in more remote, previously less tourist-developed locations.

In recent years, discourses in favour of sustainable development and decarbonisation seem to have gained even greater relevance on the political agenda, which suggests that by mid-century the

Canary Islands should reduce CO₂ emissions and become a carbon sink. This process is outlined in the Climate Action Master Plan and is also referenced in the newly approved Regional Strategy against Climate Change. Both documents promote the quantification of nature and the assignment of economic value to it for the purpose of protection. In parallel, the regional government has engaged in a strategy to create and promote a form of "green" tourism—known as "blue tourism", which incorporates environmental pretexts for coastal and marine conservation—as an alternative to traditional sun-and-beach tourism.

Specifically, on the island of Tenerife, these processes can be illustrated in the rural area of El Rincón, where the safeguarding of the agricultural landscape is linked to increased revenue extraction from tourism activity; also in La Tejita beach and the small port of Adeje, where the supposedly sustainable nature of luxury tourism infrastructure construction is justified through arguments such as environmental restoration of an adjacent natural area, relocation of protected species to other sites, low building density, and the use of sustainable materials. The "green" arguments gain even more force in the proposed theme park project on the Punta Blanca coast, which is presented as an initiative for research, environmental education, and the regeneration of the seabed and its fauna.

Case 4. Conflicts over the Management of Protected Areas in the Iberá Wetlands (Corrientes, Argentina)

The Iberá Wetlands comprise one of the largest wetland systems in Argentina, covering approximately 12,300 km² in the province of Corrientes. This ecosystem is a focus of interest due to its abundance of water, biodiversity, and varied landscapes. Around it, a complex web of interests, practices, institutions, meanings, and regulations has developed, with competing uses of water and other common goods. These include conservation projects involving the creation of protected areas and the reintroduction of species, led by state agencies, private actors, and national and international non-governmental organisations.

In 1983, the provincial government created the Iberá Nature Reserve, and in 2007, during the process of constitutional reform in the province, the Iberá Wetlands were incorporated as strategic natural and cultural heritage. In 2009, a provincial park of 482,000 hectares was established within the reserve with the aim of creating a stricter conservation core. The territory covered by the provincial reserve also contains national protected areas, a Ramsar site, private reserves, and species reintroduction projects.

Within the provincial reserve, productive activities such as rice cultivation, tourism, exotic tree plantations (eucalyptus and pine), and extensive cattle ranching take place. Cattle ranching was traditionally managed communally—large areas shared by several families—but this practice is tending to disappear due to land concentration processes and the advance of other economic activities. Except for cattle ranching, productive activities have increased in recent decades, despite their negative environmental impacts.

According to previous studies, some authors argue that, alongside the expansion of forestry projects—some aimed at carbon capture—tourism developments and the creation of protected areas in the region have triggered processes of “green grabbing” and land concentration, displacement of small producers, stronger integration of the territory into international markets, purchase of land in community territories by private actors, and the displacement of traditional activities.

Case 5. Market-Based Instruments for Conservation in Misiones, Argentina

The province of Misiones, Argentina, located within the Atlantic Forest ecoregion, combines productive landscapes (such as yerba mate cultivation and forestry, among others) with forest conservation areas that support these productive activities. Traditional conservation initiatives relate to the creation of protected areas at national, provincial, municipal, and private levels, including a green corridor, a biosphere reserve, and other legal designations that form a dense network of protected spaces.

Recently, new market-based conservation instruments have been adopted by the local government in order to harmonise productive activities with environmental sustainability, in line with commitments made at the supranational (international) level. One such approach is the reduction of risk in conservation activities through environmental insurance, facilitated by the state. This is particularly relevant for biodiversity conservation efforts, and Misiones stands out as an example due to its public policies on biodiversity.

Currently, a pilot programme is underway—intended to be implemented at provincial and regional levels—that aims to reconcile cattle ranching with the habitat of the jaguar (*Panthera onca*), compensating producers whose livestock is attacked by the feline, in order to reduce retaliatory killings by producers.

This measure, apparently focused on conserving a flagship species of both provincial and global conservation interest, also minimises risks for cattle ranching in areas where the jaguar lives. In turn, indemnified producers are also required to adopt preventive measures such as installing electric fencing or using loud noises to deter the animals.

Similar to what has occurred in the Paraná River Delta in Buenos Aires, this case illustrates the convergence of supranational interests (such as the involvement of internationally affiliated environmental organisations advocating for jaguar conservation) with the practices of local producers whose livelihoods may be affected. Finally, the case highlights the need for interjurisdictional coordination between provinces, the national government, and even between countries—particularly Brazil and Paraguay—given that the species roams freely across borders.

Recommendations

1 **Interdisciplinary approach.**

The complexity of social relations concerning the use and appropriation of nature demands an interdisciplinary approach. Addressing the environmental crisis requires not only biological and ecological knowledge of ecosystems to regulate appropriate uses—knowledge which is privileged in the formulation of environmental policies—but also the contributions of multiple disciplines capable of accounting for the social, economic, and productive changes required.

2 **Valuing other forms of knowledge.**

In line with the previous recommendation, the prioritisation of the natural sciences at the expense of other forms of knowledge leads not only to conflicts over modes of environmental management—as observed in the Paraná Delta cases—but also to the deterioration of environmental policies. This prioritisation contributes to a growing disconnect between environmental management models and local realities, limiting the implementation and reach of policies.

3 **Decision-making mechanisms.**

The articulation of environmental and productive dimensions is a necessary but insufficient condition for producing a sustainable development model. It is essential to incorporate the reconfiguration of the very social inequalities that characterise territories. This involves not only generating forms of community participation, but also dismantling the power mechanisms that ultimately include certain actors in decision-making while excluding others.

4 **Limitations of the concept of nature.**

The advance of market-based solutions in environmental policies—relying on the quantification, valuation, and financialisation of nature—can produce adverse processes such as the creation of sacrifice zones, land concentration, and exclusion of local populations, among others. This stems from a singular perception of nature as a product for meeting individual needs. It is therefore proposed to incorporate into environmental management other ways of conceiving nature beyond its market value, considering, for example, its cultural value. This entails involving multiple actors, even at the preparatory stages of environmental management programmes. A useful tool for this purpose is environmental land-use planning, which integrates social, environmental, and economic variables in spaces for consensus-building, to achieve sustainable land use and human well-being.

5 **The role of the state.**

The formulation, implementation, and monitoring of public environmental policies must rely on state agencies as guarantors of environmental justice for all members of society. The withdrawal of these agencies and the advance of market forces in environmental policies are problematic because, on the one hand, land appropriation and its associated rents are at stake, and, on the other, the consequences of the economic model are borne primarily by vulnerable populations.

In conclusion, building on these five recommendations, the aim is to challenge the assumption that every political initiative grounded in the concept of sustainable development necessarily has positive environmental and social impacts. A critical and multidimensional perspective is needed when designing and implementing public environmental policies.

Report 4

Political ecology of urbanization

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This report is framed within the political ecology of urbanization processes , addressing who produces what types of socio-ecological configurations and for whom these configurations are produced. Taking a broad and critical view of the environmental issue, four situations are examined, supported by empirical evidence, in order to make recommendations that guarantee the social, cultural and economic rights of inhabitants . Two of the situations are related to the contamination of watersheds, while the remaining two propose to delve into basic dimensions such as education, health, public transportation, infrastructure and the informal housing market. Methodologically, the first three cases are based on a qualitative approach, while the last prioritizes quantitative analysis. The cases are as follows:

- 1. The continued intervention of the Supreme Court of Justice in the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin sanitation case (Argentina)*
- 2. The "School of Citizen Science Applied to Water Conservation." The case of Lake Villarrica-Mallolafken (Chile)*
- 3. Peri-urban housing, the Cordón del Plata Case, Tupungato, Mendoza (Argentina)*
- 4. Proposals to improve the urban green infrastructure of the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires (Argentina)*

1. The continued intervention of the Supreme Court of Justice in the Matanza-Riachuelo basin sanitation case

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a. The cause of sanitation of the Matanza-Riachuelo basin

The Matanza and Riachuelo river basin covers an area of approximately 2,000 km², is 64 km² long, and encompasses four communes in the southern part of the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires and fourteen municipalities in the province: Lanús, Avellaneda, Lomas de Zamora, Esteban Echeverría, La Matanza, Cañuelas, Almirante Brown, Morón, Merlo, Marcos Paz, Presidente Perón, San Vicente, General Las Heras, and Ezeiza¹⁸. Of the basin's population, more than half lack access to a sewage system, a third lack access to drinking water, and around 500,000 live in extremely precarious settlements along the riverbanks. It is the most polluted watercourse in Argentina and has been ranked as one of the ten most polluted sites in the world (Ministerio Público de la Defensa, 2015).

Figure 1: Map of the Matanza-Riachuelo basin - Source: ACUMAR (n/d)

The Matanza-Riachuelo Basin case began in 2004 when a group of residents of Villa Inflamable (Avellaneda) filed a complaint for collective environmental damage, which was filed under the name "Beatriz Mendoza et al." In 2006, in line with this case, the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin Authority was created by Law No. 26,168/2006, a tripartite government entity: ACUMAR, composed of the national government, the provincial states, and the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires. In 2008, the Supreme Court of Justice intervened in the case (declaring its jurisdiction since 2006) and issued the guilty verdict (CSJN 08-07-2008), known as the "Mendoza Ruling." In this case, the Court recognized the environmental damage suffered by the plaintiff families and held the National State, the City of Buenos Aires, and the Province of Buenos Aires responsible (SCJN, 2008). It also ordered that these governments carry out actions within their territories and established that ACUMAR would be the entity in charge of implementing the Comprehensive Environmental Sanitation Plan (PISA). This plan originally included infrastructure works, landfill cleanups, and monitoring of environmental conditions and industrial activity. In 2016, the plan was updated, and this new document incorporated the urbanization of shantytowns and settlements among its lines of action, which included a social approach to relocation as a specific line.

[18] The Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area is made up of the city of Buenos Aires and three of the so-called "cordones" (rings) of the Greater Buenos Aires area, comprising a total of 24 municipalities. In local slang, the term "conurbano bonaerense" (the Buenos Aires metropolitan area) refers to the various municipalities located in the belts surrounding the city of Buenos Aires and extending the city into the province's interior.

The Court also ordered the creation of a Collegiate Body, composed of representatives from the following organizations (participants as interested third parties during the judicial process): La Boca Neighborhood Association (AVLB), Environment and Natural Resources Foundation (FARN), Center for Legal and Social Studies (CELS), Citizens' Association for Human Rights (ACDH), and Greenpeace (an organization that later separated from the group). This Collegiate Body, coordinated by the National Ombudsman, was charged with channeling citizen participation in monitoring compliance with the ruling.

Figure 2: Table of actors in the Matanza-Riachuelo basin
Source: Public Defense Ministry (2025)

Two key milestones can be identified regarding relocations within the framework of the aforementioned case. First, in 2010, the "Framework Agreement for the Implementation of the Urbanization Plan for Slums and Precarious Settlements at Environmental Risk in the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin" was signed between the national government, the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, and all the municipalities of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area (ACUMAR, 2010b). In this document, each local government outlined the number of families to be relocated. A total of 17,771 families were affected. Second, in 2017, the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin Authority drafted the Protocol for Addressing Relocation and Redevelopment Processes in Slums and Precarious Settlements in the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin.¹⁹ This protocol establishes that relocations are "planned processes of population displacement that respond to reasons of environmental risk or that are essential as part of a process of reurbanization of a town or settlement" (17). For this organization, relocations must be "the last alternative" (21), that is, each local government must take into account the impact that uprooting causes in the families involved, which is why it must be an action to be implemented when, for reasons of force majeure —such as floods— there are no other possible risk mitigation actions. If relocations must be implemented at all costs, the Protocol defines the guidelines and guiding principles, as well as the steps of the social and technical approach to be developed at each stage of the process. For almost 16 years, the various public policies established in the aforementioned Comprehensive Environmental Sanitation Plan were controlled by the Supreme Court in the process of executing sentences directly or through its delegated judges²⁰

[19] Approved by ACUMAR Presidential Resolution No. 420/E. 2017. Published in the Official Gazette on 12/22/2017.

[20] From 2007 to 2012, the Mendoza case was handled by an enforcement judge, Dr. Armella of the Quilmes Federal Court. He played a key role in the actions regarding population relocation, using the towpath (35 meters along the Riachuelo River), thus prioritizing the shantytown problem through measurement techniques to determine who was inside or outside this demarcation line. This federal judge was later removed from the case due to allegations of irregularities in the contracting of sanitation and infrastructure projects. He was replaced in 2012 by two other federal judges, who were assigned different functions related to sanitation. One of them was responsible for overseeing the implementation of the relocation policies for the population residing in the affected shantytowns.

On October 22, 2024, without consulting the parties involved, the Supreme Court of Justice announced that it had concluded its oversight of the case involving the contamination of the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin, after the Court filed separate complaints alleging noncompliance with the judgment by the condemned states. It stated that its intervention had already concluded with the approval of the Comprehensive Environmental Sanitation Plan and the creation of the Matanza Riachuelo Basin Authority (ACUMAR). It also "established that, henceforth, oversight of the Matanza Riachuelo Basin Authority's activities must be channeled through the channels established in Law 26,168 [the law creating ACUMAR] (...) and the oversight procedure for the activities of the entire national public administration" (Supreme Court of Justice, Judgment of April 22, 2024: 27 and 40). It should be noted that, in the following months, a large number of ACUMAR workers were dismissed, primarily those responsible for social support in the territories. For their part, the organizations that have been supporting the case since its inception, along with advocacy organizations and affected residents, organized to appeal the decision. Specifically, the Public Defense Office of the Buenos Aires City (CABA), along with the human rights organizations that comprise the Collegiate Body,²¹ filed a complaint against the Argentine State before the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights (IACHR)²² for violating the rights of the basin's inhabitants affected by the contamination. In particular the rights to a healthy environment, to water, to clean air, to life and integrity, to health, to adequate housing, to children, and to access to information, as well as judicial guarantees and judicial protection for families living in the basin" (CELS, 2025). Consequently, the organizations request measures aimed at guaranteeing these rights and precautionary measures to protect the health of the basin's inhabitants.

b. Academic studies in the Matanza-Riachuelo basin

The study of involuntary relocation processes has been a discreetly developed field from Anthropology and other related disciplines, mainly in its connection with large-scale projects (Bartolomé, 1985; Ferradas, 1990; Catullo, 2006). More recent works focus, specifically, on relocations in the Matanza-Riachuelo basin (Carman, 2017; Scharager, 2017; Najman and Fainstein, 2018; Olejarczyk, 2023).

Carman (2017) examines the relocations implemented by the City Housing Institute (IVC) between 2010 and 2015 in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires. Initially, these processes were more like evictions, but over the years, based on pressure from territorial actors and some state agents, they evolved into more participatory experiences, although not without difficulties and conflicts. Scharager (2017) analyzed the relocations in the Matanza-Riachuelo basin in slum 21-24. The author focuses on the interrelationship between the various actors involved and the meanings at stake in a single relocation process.

Najman and Fainstein (2018) analyze the relocation of residents of Villa 21-24 to the Barrio Padre Mugica housing complex, its effects, and how the relocation process connected with historical struggles for habitat and housing.

Finally, Olejarczyk (2023) analyzed the relocation processes in the middle Matanza-Riachuelo basin. The author focuses her analysis on the category of "environmental risk" that guides relocation processes throughout the basin. She expresses that this category is not only produced and reproduced culturally and collectively within the framework of the cause (Douglas, 1996) but, in addition, operates a native category that guides – at least enunciatively – the public policy of relocations within said process and that enables differential access to housing produced by the local government, (Fonseca and Cardarelli, 2005; Verón, 2011; Olejarczyk, 2020).

[21] These are: the Center for Legal and Social Studies (CELS), the Environment and Natural Resources Foundation (FARN), the Citizens' Association for Human Rights (ACDH), the La Boca Neighborhood Association (AVLB), and the TEMAS Foundation.

[22] The IACHR is an organ of the Organization of American States (OAS) responsible for the promotion and protection of human rights.

c. Evidence. Current data regarding the implementation of relocations

- According to the Matanza Riachuelo Basin Authority's official website, the completion of housing solutions will reach 43% by early 2025.
- The completion of 57% of the necessary relocations remains pending, along with all the necessary repairs, final improvements, and urbanizations.
- The implementation of the so-called Riachuelo System remains pending. This project is essential for providing adequate water and sewage services to the south of the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires and part of the Greater Buenos Aires area, as well as for treating the organic waste that pollutes the Riachuelo.
- There is no budget allocated for the year 2025.
- Since December 2023, with the new administration of the National State, the Matanza Riachuelo Basin Authority has been depleted of resources and staff.
- According to estimates by the Matanza Riachuelo Basin Authority itself, based on the various delays, all of the promised housing solutions would not be completed until 2049.²³

d. Recommendations for the protection and guarantee of the social, cultural and economic rights of the inhabitants of the basin

Given all of the above, the end of the Supreme Court's oversight of the case is of great concern in the most significant environmental damage case in Argentine history, amid a context of the depletion of the State and the implementation of public policies.

In light of this, and in order to guarantee and safeguard the rights of the inhabitants of the Matanza-Riachuelo basin, it is recommended that:

- The Supreme Court of Justice resumes supervision in the case, in order to control the compliance of the states in their obligations aimed at guaranteeing the adoption of measures to protect the health of the inhabitants of the Matanza Riachuelo Basin.
- The Matanza Riachuelo Basin Authority and local governments must carry out the necessary actions to execute 100% of the planned relocations, ensuring that they are carried out in a participatory manner while safeguarding the social, cultural, and economic rights of the affected population and through effective improvements in their quality of life, as established by the regulatory frameworks approved within the framework of the case (PISA 2016 and the Relocation Protocol 2017).

[23] Resolution of the Federal Court of Morón No. 2 of June 30, 2023.

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2. The “School of Citizen Science Applied to Water Conservation.” The case of Lake Villarrica- Mallolafken , Chile

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a. The problem of Lake Villarrica - Mallolafken

Lake Villarrica is located in the Araucanía region, Chile. It is part of a sub-basin from East to West, located between the Andes Mountains and the Pacific Ocean. It belongs to the hydrographic basin of the Toltén River, encompassing the communes of Villarrica, Pucón, Curarrehue and Cunco (Goich , Muñoz, Saravia; 2021). It is of vital importance in different spheres, both at the ecosystem level, as a habitat of great biodiversity²⁴, in addition to being the main axis generating tourism in the region, it plays a fundamental role in the development of surrounding communes and represents a milestone for the inhabitants of the territory at the landscape level. The Lake Villarrica basin is classified as an area of tourist interest, highlighting that it is part of the Araucarias Biosphere Reserve recognized by UNESCO, and in turn, two national parks are located there (Goich , Muñoz, Saravia; 2021). However, it is a water source that faces an ecological risk. Pollution in Lake Villarrica- Mallolafken has reached critical levels in recent years, making it the first lake in the country to be declared a "Saturated Zone" by the Ministry of the Environment.²⁴ This declaration is based on exceeding the parameters regulated by the Secondary Environmental Quality Standard;²⁵ specifically in the concentrations of chlorophyll "a", transparency, and dissolved phosphorus, evidencing an accelerated process of eutrophication, the origin of which is mainly attributable to human activities in the basin (MMA-UFRO, 2018; Escobar, 2019). Among the point sources of pollution, the aquaculture industry is identified, through emissions from 16 fish farms in the basin, as well as discharges from the sewage system of the Curarrehue commune , which has no treatment, and those associated with the wastewater treatment plant (PTA) of the Pucón commune, in addition, among the diffuse sources, the infiltrations of wastewater from individual treatment systems in homes, population overload in high season, together with forestry and agricultural activities and deforestation of the native forest are identified, these include indirect causes, which respond to surface and subsurface runoff, intensified by the various land uses in the basin (Escobar, 2019).

This scenario motivated the development of the first Decontamination Plan for an aquatic environment in Chile, with the goal of reversing pollution levels and achieving the standards established by current regulations.²⁶ Although the Plan includes measures such as point source control, diffuse source control, indirect nutrient management measures, emissions offsets, an operational plan for algal blooms, a citizen engagement program, complementary programs, and monitoring of plan compliance, certain complaints remain. As a new regulation for fish farm emissions, riverbank reforestation, and the improvement of upstream treatment systems, its formulation process has been questioned due to the difficulties and challenges involved in an effective and informed citizen participation process, despite the existence of the Expanded Operating Committee. The Plan's implementation is taking place within a regulatory context marked by the prioritization of economic growth over environmental protection, under a neoliberal model that conceives nature as a consumer and exploitation good (Shiva, 1995; Svampa and Viale, 2017; MAI, 2021). The permissiveness of industries that are not compatible with state-protected wilderness areas, the scarce state oversight of privately managed treatment plants, and weak regulation of rural domestic water treatment have increased the vulnerability of the ecosystem and directly affected the health of local communities. The lack of territorial planning has allowed for massive and

[24] Supreme Decree No. 43 of October 19, 2017.

[25] Secondary Environmental Quality Standard DS. No. 19/2013 MMA.

[26] Secondary Environmental Quality Standard DS. No. 19/2013 MMA.

unregulated real estate expansion, especially on the southern shore of the lake and in rural areas, with construction even taking place within the lake area, a situation highlighted by the Comptroller General's Office. Added to this is the impact of intensive and unregulated tourism, which has exacerbated ecosystem and landscape deterioration, reducing the environmental and social quality of the territory. Faced with this situation, social organizations and citizen movements have played a fundamental role in raising awareness of this problem and demanding more effective and participatory actions.

In response to this form of development, which affects both the way people live and the ecosystems of the territory, an active social fabric has emerged that rejects the imposition of high-impact projects implemented without citizen participation. Thus, citizen movements have taken concrete action against real estate expansion, road construction, mining, and hydroelectric projects, clearly speaking out against this development model. Actions by social organizations and citizen movements have not been limited solely to opposing projects, but have also developed comprehensive and ongoing work in the area. This work seeks to integrate formal technical information with local knowledge of the area to generate concrete proposals and actions. The areas of the Villarrica- Mallolafken watershed have particularly stood out for implementing numerous citizen environmental campaigns, including interventions before the Municipal Council, the Regional Ministerial Secretariat (SEREMI), and the Ministry of the Environment, as well as public discussions, citizen research, environmental education programs, and campaigns against real estate projects that affect wetlands and the lake. These experiences reflect a committed and active social fabric that has significantly influenced public policies and territorial planning processes at the local and national levels. However, there remains an urgent need to ensure real and binding citizen participation in water care, fully integrating the voices, perspectives, and worldviews of territorial actors as an essential part of environmental democracy. The experience and vision of social organizations, which promote a different approach to the environment, are essential for moving toward more just, equitable, and sustainable management of the land and its water resources. It is worth highlighting the fundamental role that the Mapuche people play in the care and protection of the land.

b. Evidence of the problem in water care

The environmental crisis affecting the Villarrica Lake basin reflects the profound limitations of current public policies to address the problem from a sustainable local development perspective, highlighting the lack of effective coordination between territorial actors, authorities, and local communities. In this context, the proposal for local development, understood as a multidimensional and participatory process, appears as a necessary alternative to the dominant economic model that prioritizes extractivism and capital accumulation over environmental protection and social well-being (Shiva, 1995; Svampa and Viale, 2014). Local development should not be limited solely to economic growth, but should seek to generate territorial transformation processes that recognize the diversity of social actors, their knowledge, and their ways of inhabiting the territory (Chauca and López, 2004). From this perspective, economic, sociocultural, and environmental dimensions are integrated, placing the active participation of communities as a central axis to guarantee the sustainability of actions and the relevance of responses to local problems (Delgado, Bachmann, & Oñate, 2007). The connection between territory, citizenship, and the environment becomes fundamental, recognizing that ecosystemic and social dynamics are interdependent and cannot be thought of as separate fields. In this sense, participation is not understood solely as presence, but as an active and transformative process of power relations, where social actors acquire a real capacity to influence decisions that affect their lives and their environment (Linares, Mora, & Correa, 2007). This participation is realized in the creation of spaces for deliberation, commitment, and shared responsibility, allowing communities to cease being mere spectators to become leading agents of social and environmental change (El Troudi, Harnecker, & Bonilla, 2005). Thus, participation is conceived as a practice that articulates collective action with the subjective dimensions of each actor, enhancing the construction of identity and self-management (Serra, 2010).

Within this logic, environmental democracy and participatory management become key elements for the development of effective and socially legitimized public policies. The involvement of communities in decision-making facilitates more transparent administration that is adapted to local needs and capacities, promoting alternatives that emerge from the territories and knowledge themselves, and not imposed by external market logics (Castillo, 2000; Salazar, 2011). Social actors, understood as collective subjects aware of their identity, bearers of values and action strategies, are fundamental in this process (Pérez, 1995; Portilla, 2003). Their capacity to organize, generate discourses, raise demands, and propose alternatives from the territory, gives them a decisive role in the construction of transformation scenarios. This collective force, far from being homogeneous, is nourished by the diversity of trajectories, knowledge and experiences that each actor contributes, constituting a dynamic network that connects past, present and future in the search for a common project (Braffo, 2010).

In the specific case of the Mallolafken basin, there is a strong collective interest in actively participating in these processes, although it faces several significant challenges that hinder effective participation. These challenges include a lack of horizontality in dialogue spaces and the difficulty in establishing truly inclusive participation. Furthermore, institutional spaces, such as those linked to the Environmental Decontamination Plan, are often limited in time, use inaccessible language, and tend to oversimplify problems, which generates biases in citizen representation and hinders access to clear and understandable information. In this context, and given the profound environmental crisis facing the Villarrica basin, the collaboration between the University of La Frontera, the Municipality of Pucón, and civil society has given rise to the "School of Citizen Science, Applied to Water Care." This is an initiative that seeks to promote environmental education from a participatory approach, focused on action and commitment to the territory. This first version of the school brought together seven young people between the ages of 14 and 16 from the lake area, who actively participated in a pedagogical proposal that combines practical experimentation with critical reflection, promoting the formation of a generation aware of and connected to the socio-environmental challenges of the local ecosystem. The project, led by Loreto Lagos Sanhueza, a professor at the Pucón Campus, aims to open a space for dialogue and learning for young people interested in science and the environment, establishing the possibility of this experience being maintained over time as a permanent environmental education program for socio-ecological restoration. Through the methodology of citizen science, the project seeks to reduce the understanding gap regarding the lake's problems and strengthen the role of young people as active agents in the search for solutions.

In this context, during the month of January, the "School of Citizen Science" developed a series of six practical workshops that combined the assessment of prior knowledge with field trips for sample analysis, inquiry and experimentation sessions, and spaces dedicated to dialogue, reflection, and communication of results. This methodological proposal focused on learning from direct experience, allowing not only for greater appropriation of knowledge but also for the construction of a critical and committed awareness regarding the environmental situation of the lake. Progress was evident both in the understanding of the topics addressed and in the active involvement of the participants, who continue to conduct monthly water quality monitoring. These sessions incorporated interviews, spaces for reflection, and projections to deepen understanding of the social and ecohydrological relationships of the territory, contributing from a situated and participatory educational perspective to local management processes. The interviews conducted revealed valuable information for the young people and highlighted a worrying lack of information regarding socio-environmental issues. Through this process, their empowerment in managing environmental information has been strengthened, expanding their action and communication capabilities. At the end of this first phase, the need to share what they had learned clearly emerged, demonstrating a growing sense of responsibility and involvement.

The project is supported by the Municipality of Pucón, through its Department of Sanitation, Environment, and Ornamentation, together with the Union of Urban Neighborhood Associations of Pucón and the Center for Water Management and Technologies of the University of La Frontera. This inter-institutional alliance reinforces the goal of coordinating academic knowledge with local experiences, fostering active community participation in the processes of diagnosis, protection, and recovery of the territory's socio-ecological balance. All of this is framed within the greater challenge of moving toward more horizontal, inclusive, and participatory management.

However, structural obstacles persist, such as the lack of access to understandable technical information, the circulation of inaccurate content in the media, and the denial of the problem in key areas of the territory, particularly in the tourism sector, which limits the development of a fully informed and engaged citizenry.

c. Recommendations associated with effective participation

From this experience, several recommendations emerge to strengthen decision-making and the design of public policies with a territorial focus.

- The proposal is to advance the creation and strengthening of a Municipal Water Affairs Office, as a technical and citizen-based body to channel complaints, coordinate proposals, and coordinate actions among citizens, public institutions, and river basin councils. This office, supported as a priority proposal by the General Directorate of Water, would address the current lack of local spaces dedicated to water participation and governance, in addition to disseminating training programs and facilitating access to clear and timely environmental information.
- We recommend extending experiences such as the "Citizen Science School" to high schools and colleges in the region, integrating its methodology into formal education programs. This involves developing in-depth learning about water from an ecohydrological perspective, fostering a comprehensive understanding of its cycles, functions, and social relations. Including sections of rivers or wetlands by school or sector in the region would also allow for the creation of emotional bonds with ecosystems and foster a paradigm shift regarding water as a living and common element. It is essential to strengthen local actions from a situated territorial perspective. Intervention in tributaries, wetlands, or micro-basins linked to active communities represents an opportunity to deploy synergistic strategies that connect diverse learning, resources, and stakeholders. This integration would allow each action to be integrated into a broader vision of territorial restoration and governance, combining capacities from the community to the institutional level.
- It is of utmost importance to move toward a management approach to natural heritage and protected wilderness areas based on prevention rather than reaction. It is urgent to develop institutional proposals to ensure the conservation of wetlands and biodiversity zones, especially in the face of scenarios of reduced water availability associated with climate change. At the same time, incorporating water quality monitoring in these ecosystems as a basis for building baselines and protection plans will enable us to move toward a more equitable, proactive, and sustainable management model.
- At the same time, it is recommended to rethink the perspective of tourism in the basin. The tourism sector's responsibility for water conservation must go beyond rhetoric and translate into concrete practices, integrating tourism companies and workers into environmental education processes, citizen monitoring, and communication of local issues. This task also requires developing qualified human capital to engage in areas that have historically been resistant to ecosystem care, thus opening new avenues for collaboration.

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3. Peri-urban housing, the Cordón del Plata Case, Tupungato, Mendoza, Argentina

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a. The stages of settlement in the neighborhood and the tensions in the forms of access to housing

The Cordón del Plata area, located in the Tupungato department of the Mendoza Province, is located on Route 96, 18 km from the city of Tupungato. The first stage of settlement began with a cooperative initiative, primarily involving agricultural workers from the area. In the initial stage, the Cooperative purchased the land in 1987 and later donated it to the Municipality. Once the land became state-owned, it could be surveyed and specific urban development work undertaken. Through this legal process, the Municipality of Tupungato was able to recognize this previously productive land as intended for housing, legalizing the subdivision and legitimizing the ownership of the future homes. It is important to note that this process, in turn, made it possible to build the homes through a mortgage loan granted by a state agency. Over the following decades, the neighborhood known as "El Álamo" grew and encompassed several different neighborhoods, the result of varied histories and processes. Therefore, the history of this area is composed of different stages of settlement in particular contexts carried out by specific social groups (Mingo and Berger, 2025). In 2001, houses were handed over in the second neighborhood, called Barrio "Norte," which, as we shall see, were destined for the daughters and sons of the residents of the first neighborhood, "El Álamo."

Approximately a decade later, the "Integración" neighborhood was built, meeting municipal requirements. Like the previous neighborhoods, the homes were built with state mortgage loans. It is important to note that the origins of the "Integración" neighborhood are different from the two previous ones, as it was a solution, offered by the municipality, to a conflict between families and a private producer over a land occupation located on privately owned land near the Cordón del Plata. In this case, the relocation of the families caused some conflicts between the original inhabitants and the new families relocated to the Cordón.

The two remaining neighborhoods, which complete the current configuration of the Cordón del Plata, are "Loteo Bazán" and "Amigos y Vecinos." These neighborhoods originated in irregular subdivisions, according to both municipal officials and long-time residents of the area. In both neighborhoods, where the population of Bolivian origin predominates, differences can be observed in both the subdivision and the water and electricity service infrastructure. Likewise, the housing construction and the uses given to them by their inhabitants show differences with the neighborhoods described above.

Below, we present on the map the location of the different neighborhoods and the main institutions where interaction takes place in the area known as the "Cordón del Plata."

Figure 3: Map of the Cordón del Plata neighborhood
 Source: Prepared by the author based on the Google Earth platform.

Differences in access to housing and, above all, the Municipality's involvement in the design, construction, and provision of services in neighborhoods explain some of the conflicts, both structural and neighborhood-related, that develop in everyday life in the Cordón del Plata neighborhood.

Among the inhabitants of the first neighborhoods ("El Álamo" and "Norte"), built through the collective land purchase process and in partnership with the Municipality, their legitimacy as a community stands out not only for being "original" inhabitants of the area but also as those who obtained their homes through their own economic efforts. This does not mean that the cooperative project does not contain disagreements and conflicts attributed to irregularities on the part of both the cooperative members and the municipality. In general, they attribute to this process, to its protagonists, and to their heirs the legitimate ways of inhabiting the Cordón del Plata. From these representations, they construct, for example, the inhabitants of the "Integración" neighborhood as those who gained access to housing through extortionate actions such as land seizures. However, the inhabitants of the "Integración" neighborhood state that they paid for their homes through loans granted by the municipality. In turn, the "stigmatization" of the "Integración" neighborhood is shared by residents of the "Bazán" and "Amigos y Vecinos" neighborhoods, who emphasize that they built their homes with their own efforts and labor and that "nothing has been given to them" like their neighbors. In addition to questioning access to housing, residents of both the initial two neighborhoods and those of the "Bazán" and "Amigos y Vecinos" neighborhoods characterize the Integración neighborhood as inhabited by "conflictive and criminal" individuals. These stigmatizations crystallized in a conflict over a robbery followed by a murder that was attributed to residents of the Integración neighborhood. These classifications are observed, for example, in the use of community spaces and in the distribution of shops and fairs along the Cordón del Plata. Below, we outline the main aspects, including tensions and conflicts, around which the Cordón del Plata neighborhood is configured as a territory where social, economic, and political processes converge.

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b. The problem of the Cordón del Plata as a territorial expression

The continued population increase is putting a strain on state-provided services in sectors such as education, health, public transportation, infrastructure projects, and the informal housing market.

Education:

In Cordón del Plata, there is one kindergarten and another soon to be opened, a primary school, and a secondary school that began operating in 2008. The growing demand for primary school places forces children to attend primary schools near the neighborhood. Because the distances are between 5 and 10 kilometers, the Municipality provides transportation for children to nearby towns. The contribution of transportation is crucial for the continuity of primary education, since the public service does not have the necessary frequency to these towns.

Secondary education is provided by the local secondary school. The challenge for young people is continuing on to higher education. In this case, distance and transportation costs are among the biggest problems. Higher education options are limited to those offered by tertiary institutions in both Tupungato and Tunuyán. Access to university education entails medium-distance travel, with high costs for families.

Health:

Cordón del Plata has a primary care center with daily medical and nursing services. During the week, various specialists attend, and the most complex situations are treated at the Tunuyán Hospital or, occasionally, at the hospital in Mendoza City, the provincial capital. The neighborhood also has an ambulance for emergency transfers. For scheduled medical care, residents of Cordón del Plata must provide their own transportation or use public transportation, which entails costs for families and inconvenient transfers for people with reduced mobility. It is important to note that births take place at the Tunuyán Hospital. Furthermore, it is interesting to note that the distance to the hospital complicates the support and care strategies for patients' families.

Public transport:

Transportation is a cross-cutting issue when analyzing the ways people live in peri-urban areas. Residents of the Cordón del Plata region are heavily dependent on public transportation for their mobility. Among the most significant issues related to public transportation are the cost, frequency, and restricted routes used by public buses. This means that residents must travel long distances on foot to reach relatively nearby towns that are not connected by the transportation network. The area also has private transportation, although not always regulated, that covers some transportation needs.

Infrastructure works and informal housing market:

One of the main problems observed is related to the informal land market for housing, where a private agent subdivides land and sells the plots, but it is not possible to survey and subdivide the land to obtain the property title. Due to legal restrictions, the Municipality cannot provide basic services in informal subdivisions and on land classified as "productive" rather than "residential." This interweaving of situations causes families to suffer for several months from the lack of basic services such as electricity, running water, and waste collection. This disconnect between the need for access to housing and the legal requirements for providing services to the territories creates the need to create organizations representing civil society through which appropriate legal entities can be created to grant these territories the status of "residential." This strategy was implemented in the "Bazán" and "Amigos y Vecinos" neighborhoods, led by the Bolivian community. Through these union figures, they were able to formalize water service for the entire neighborhood and organize a monthly collection to pay the bill among all residents. These meetings, driven by need, result in roles that, while not previously expected, consolidate leadership within the population, which are re-emerged as new demands arise from the neighborhoods toward the State.

c. Recommendations for the Cordón del Plata

- Improve the number of primary school vacancies in the Cordón del Plata area.
- Provide low-cost transportation services for youth access to higher education.
- Streamline municipal requirements for the provision of public services in the "Bazán" and "Amigos y Vecinos" neighborhoods.
- Extend public transportation service routes in general and improve their frequency so that residents can get around.
- Increase specialist care in the Neighborhood Health Room.
- Increase the availability of transportation to referral health centers in Tunuyán or Mendoza. It is important to keep in mind that these distances complicate the provision of care and support to family members of those treated at health centers far from the Cordón del Plata neighborhood.

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4. Proposals to improve urban green infrastructure in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires

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a. Evidence: current data on urban green infrastructure

The Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, capital of the Argentine Republic and central nucleus of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area, covers an area of approximately 200 km² organized into 15 communes and 48 neighborhoods, nominated based on the ecclesiastical parishes established during the 19th century. According to national censuses, its population has experienced marginal variations since the first population census carried out in 1947, registering 2,890,151 inhabitants in 2010 and 3,120,612 in 2022. This demographic stability, associated with its territorial extension, places it among the twenty most densely populated cities in the world, with an estimated value of 15 thousand inhabitants per km².

In this context of population pressure, urban green infrastructure—understood as the interconnected network of natural areas in urban spaces—takes on special relevance, especially considering the positive effects it generates, which have recently been termed ecosystem services. Official records indicate an increase in the area of green space per inhabitant, rising from 5 m²/inhabitant (2002) to 7 m²/inhabitant (2023). However, not only is the green area reduced, but definitions, typologies, and data collection methods have also changed (Gallardo Araya, 2016).²⁷ Added to this is the lack of rigor in the record-keeping, as evidenced by the case of urban gardens, which do not appear as a distinct category either in the aforementioned typologies or in the national agricultural censuses. Despite this omission, a national program recorded between 430 and 620 evictions (formal, mixed, and informal) between 2002 and 2012, while other studies have documented evictions resulting from municipal actions (Gallardo Araya, 2016, 2021). An urban agriculture law (Law No. 6377)²⁸ was passed in 2020, but to date, all its powers have not been fully implemented.

Source: Statistical Yearbook (2021)

[27] The internationally recommended green space values vary between 10 and 15 m², despite this, however, some authors point out that the World Health Organization has never officially stated on the matter (Rodríguez and Vásquez Brust, 2022).

[28] Here we are referring to the Integrated Project for the Promotion of Self-Production of Food—better known as ProHuerta—which constitutes one of the fundamental public policies for understanding urban agricultural practices. This program was formulated in 1990 by the National Institute of Agricultural Technology (INTA) during Argentina's hyperinflation, despite the fact that experts were already aware of the controversies regarding the limited impact that small-scale self-production of food could generate.

Trees constitute another relevant aspect in the analysis of urban green infrastructure. The nation's capital presents a spatially heterogeneous vegetation layer composed of wild-growing, cultivated, remnant, and "new nature" species, located in abandoned and/or deliberately reclaimed sites (Faggi , n.d.). Within this group, trees stand out as one of the most studied components, given that their registration in public tree censuses responds to the need for inspection, maintenance, and management due to the dangers they can pose to the community. This categorization includes both trees located in common green spaces and those located on sidewalks or pavements, known as alignment trees. They are currently regulated under Law 3263, passed in 2009.

Despite their importance, the information available in the city of Buenos Aires is limited: the data are not publicly accessible, and there are discrepancies in the reported figures. Furthermore, some studies show a historical downward trend: the last census conducted in 2017 recorded a total of 431,326 trees, lower than the 450,000 documented in the 1940s, a period after which the population remained relatively stable (Gallardo Araya and Drovandi , 2020 and in press).

These values are considerably low compared to what other cities propose. The tree-per-inhabitant ratio indicates a value of 0.13 for linear trees and 0.15 if park and square trees are added. That is, we have 150 public trees per 1,000 inhabitants, when the minimum recommended value is 2,000 per 1,000 (Ledesma, 2008). Regarding the inverse ratio, in different cities in France, the number of people sharing a tree is estimated to be between 10 and 48 inhabitants; in Austria, it is closer to 12 and 21 inhabitants (Pauleit et al., 2005). In Madrid, the ratio reaches 11.1; in New York, 13.8; and in Bogotá, 18.74 (Tovar-Corzo, 2013). Meanwhile, in Buenos Aires, the value found is 7 inhabitants per tree (Gallardo Araya and Drovandi , in press). Added to the low tree population are the problems associated with biodiversity. Census records show an increase of 43 species between 2000 and 2010. However, this quantitative increase did not translate into a significant qualitative improvement, as the American ash (*Fraxinus officinalis*) persists in number. *pennsylvanica* , 38.05%), which represents a central problem in urban forestry management for two reasons: it impoverishes the landscape heritage and generates ecological imbalances (Ledesma, 2008).

This analysis critically examines the evolution of environmental policies in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, within the context of the growing importance of environmental issues on national and international public agendas. The constant reappropriation and discursive redefinition of environmental concepts by multiple actors is in line with the new environmental issue, which has taken shape internationally since the Stockholm Conference (1972). Our team analyzes key manifestations of this same phenomenon, such as the conflicts that have arisen between protected natural areas and the inhabitants of various slums (Carman , 2011, Carman et al. 2016), the extraction of real estate rents (Wertheimer, 2020), and the aforementioned relocations of the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin (Carman , 2017; Olejarczyk , 2020 and 2023). From this approach, it is observed that the environmental policies associated with the urban green infrastructure of the city of Buenos Aires show a counterpoint between what is said and what is finally done with the slogan of "the green city", and this is evidenced by three issues: (a) a lack of timely dissemination of public information, (b) a partial survey of data coupled with inconsistencies, and (c) the absence of verifiable comprehensive improvements. This problem is aggravated in public trees due to the recent hiring of private companies and transnational agents in strategic functions (such as pruning, planting and surveys) (Gallardo Araya and Drovandi , in press).

In short, not only is there a reduced quantity, quality, and accessibility of urban green infrastructure, but there is also a documented downward and uneven trend in the distribution of green spaces and public trees across the city's various neighborhoods. This problem has prompted persistent complaints from experts and neighborhood organizations—such as the "Basta de Mutilar" collective—who denounce, among other issues, not only the inadequacy of planting but also the inadequate, repeated, and systematic pruning carried out by private companies that fail to comply with technical assessments of the trees.²⁹ Such interventions, in addition to compromising the phytosanitary and mechanical condition of urban trees, pose a risk to public safety due to the potential for tree fall.

[29] In fact, in 2017, an injunction was filed with the court, suspending tree pruning and felling for failure to comply with articles regulating issues such as access to information, technical evaluation of trees, and certification of the capacity of contracted personnel. This claim was upheld by a court order in 2025.

b. Recommendations for the protection of environmental rights

Based on the above, the following are general measures for urban green infrastructure, followed by specific measures for urban agriculture and public trees.

General measures associated with all green spaces:

- The municipal government—through its environmental departments—will comprehensively improve the quantity, quality, and accessibility of the urban green space, under a strategic planning model that governs short-, medium-, and long-term management, with authorities, officials, and workers specialized in the subject.
- The municipal government—through specialized municipalities—shall generate statistical information with periodic and standardized indicators that are freely and publicly accessible, allowing for monitoring and evaluating the impact of interventions in each municipality.
- The municipal government must guarantee the permanent protection of public green areas, with budget allocation, strict oversight of real estate projects, and rigorous application of administrative and criminal sanctions proportional to the potential damage caused.
- Citizens and the private sector actively contribute to urban green infrastructure through various strategies, including seeking information about the benefits and risks it poses to the entire community.

Measures focused on urban agriculture:

- The municipal government should incorporate detailed and up-to-date data on the city's agricultural practices into its urban green infrastructure statistics.
- The municipal government should suspend the eviction of urban gardens and establish formal mechanisms (agreements, permits, or licenses) in collaboration with the responsible institutions and organizations to ensure the continued existence of these spaces in the city.
- The municipal government should implement public policies with increased budget allocations. For example, a landmark case is the Green Schools Program (created in 2010), which should be allocated sufficient resources to cover basic needs such as specialized assistance, supplies, and ongoing monitoring.
- The municipal government implemented Law No. 6377, passed in 2020, which was created to promote and disseminate urban agriculture practices "to foster healthy eating habits, protect the environment, and diversify food production and consumption with sustainable methods through citizen participation." Some of the powers of the implementing authority announced in this law regulate some of the aforementioned recommendations—such as the provision of technical support—and include the creation of a list of land suitable for cultivation. Changes to this law are also suggested to address the oversight of private interests.
- The national government should reinstate the ProHuerta program cited in this document, which was discontinued at the beginning of 2024, as well as the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area Agricultural Experimental Station of the National Institute of Agricultural Technology, which will be dismantled starting in 2025, due to the importance of these institutions in promoting agricultural activities in urban environments.

Measures related to urban trees:

- The municipal government must comply with Law No. 3263 of 2009 for the implementation of a free, open, and public access computer system that provides transparency in all necessary planning, execution, and monitoring of tree species, using specialized survey personnel to avoid inconsistencies.
- The municipal government should regulate and supervise urban tree management and upkeep, paying special attention to frequent pruning, as this is not only unnecessary but also reduces the trees' life expectancy.
- The municipal government must implement a continuous and successive computerized monitoring system—replacing the decennial censuses—to record species with specialized, permanently hired personnel. To this end, it will be necessary to make certain amendments to Law No. 3263, which establishes the production of decennial censuses, which are insufficient to guarantee adequate species monitoring in the short, medium, and long term.
- The municipal government must establish a plan for the improvement, management, and maintenance of urban trees in terms of quantity and quality, including greater biological diversity and a selection of species suitable for the urban area in question, considering lighting, irrigation systems, etc.
- The municipal government should promote citizen participation, as well as inform and disseminate the importance of the tree component due to (a) the services it provides to the urban ecosystem – thus reducing inappropriate pruning and extraction – and (b) the risks it can cause to the population – falling branches and trees.

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